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Religions, Rituals, and the Heaviness of Indian History

Introduction

It is well-known that the idea of "people of the Book" (*ahl-al kitāb*) comes from the Koran. Jews, Christians and Muslims benefit from a religion founded on a celestial book, revealed to mankind by God and therefore capable of coinciding with the concept of truth ("revealed religion", "revealed truth"). However, rather than from the Koran or from the reality of facts, the idea of the three "peoples of the Book" has entered modern western political-religious conceptualization through the mediation of some sectors of orientalism. In fact, according to the Koran (XXII, 17), also the Zoroastrians, who base their identity on the *Avesta* and not on the Bible, should be considered a "people of the Book". If, at the moment of its composition, a precise interest in India had existed (as had been the case with Iran for a long time), it is not unlikely that the Archangel Gabriel would have added an abrogative verse maintaining that a sacred and revealed holy book also existed beyond the Indus, as in due time the Muslims of India would recognize, and perhaps we would not find ourselves today in the situation, absolutely paradoxical after two centuries of research, of not having even a barely comprehensible model for the interpretation of the political-religious history of India.

In the West, the concept of "peoples of the Book" was made equal to that of "monotheistic religions". According to the accepted paradigm, outside of Judaism, Christianity, and Islam there are no monotheistic systems. I will not elaborate this point here, but I think, like anyone who has experienced India and is not limited to external impressions, that to consider the Indians who participate in the Brahmanic tradition as polytheistic is, starting at least from a period that goes as far back as the composition of the oldest part of the Bible, to say the least, rash¹. I will elaborate the first point, that in India a "religion of the Book" exists,

¹ The way of conceiving the Supreme Being varies in India: from a theorization of an absolute Principle, to the somewhat abstract conception of Godhead, to the idea of a God creator and personal. As in the West, it is in opposition to these beliefs that materialist and atheist positions developed. Tucci (1977: 275 ff.) has dedicated a chapter of his *Storia della filosofia indiana* to these questions. See also Gonda (1981: 344 ff.).

and that this book is, naturally, the Veda. The awareness of preaching to the converted is very precise on my part, but I will do so all the same because there are important scholars today who would seem to negate this crucial aspect (and we will see exactly how crucial). I am referring particularly to Fritz Staal (e.g. 1983 b: 44; 1990 b: 393 ff.), whose points of view I will refer to repeatedly, being an authoritative scholar. Starting at least from the times in which the *Manusmṛiti* was written, which was the period of a very deep crisis for the Brahmanic power², the Veda has been considered as a holy text, (self)-revealed and founding the Brahmanic identity, otherwise insufficiently defined by caste or blood ties. The Veda is perceived as eternal and *apauruṣeya*, i.e. not composed by any human author. The whole universe emanates from it, and according to the *Śvetāśvatara Upaniṣad* (VI, 18) it was imparted to Brahmā by the Supreme Being (see Kane 1930-46, II, 1: 352-3). The Veda is *śruti*, revelation. According to Manu (I, 21), the triple, eternal Veda is created by God, and being *śruti*, any conflicting statements are both held to be law (II, 14). It is the source of *dharma* (defined as *sanātana*, "perennial" or "perpetual"), the *smṛti*, "tradition", coming together in its formation and normativeness (*Manusmṛiti*: II, 10; see Kane 1930-46, I, 1: 6-10). All the *smṛtis* which are not based on the Veda are declared to be founded on Darkness, and all the doctrines differing from the Veda are worthless and false (ib.: XII, 95-6). This latter is an important claim, because it indicates that the Veda, as a revealed book, marks a precise border, and in this it is no exception with respect to the revealed books of the monotheistic traditions customarily accepted as such. It, too, is held to be the foundation of the truth. As for the six *darśanas*, they are different "visions" of the Veda, each of them confirming its authority and truth in its own way.

There is nothing, up to this point, allowing us to consider the Veda in a different manner than the Bible or the Koran. A comparison can be made, for certain aspects, with Christianity (not with its Protestant expressions, however), where, in both the Catholic and Orthodox Churches, revelation and tradition (*śruti* and *smṛti*) are doctrinally and historically complementary. Because of *smṛti*, no Brahman can even think of following to the letter all the prescriptions of the Veda, which, being continuously revealed, is subject to a sort of continuous updating.

The authors of some of the most important histories of Indian philosophy and religions have underlined this. S. Dasgupta (1932-5, I: 11) explained "that the Vedas, far from being regarded as a dead literature of the past, are still looked upon as the origin and source of almost all literatures except purely secular poetry

² According to Jayaswal (1930: 40-1), it was composed at the time of Puṣyamitra Śuṅga and embodies the orthodox counter-revolution against the Mauryan state. According to Kane (1930-46, I, 1: 326), the text cannot contain material dating to before 200 B.C., and its present form was attained "at least before the 2nd century A.D." (ib.: 300). But even "a final compilation in the 2nd century A.D.", a date doubtfully accepted by Gonda (1981: 289), agrees with what is maintained in these pages: we would be at the time of the Kuṣāṇa, a foreign and - despite the attempts to integrate itself into the orthodox Indian tradition - essentially pro-Buddhist dynasty.

and drama", and that "the orthodox Hindu life may still be regarded in the main as an adumbration of the Vedic life, which had never ceased to shed its light all through the past". If we might consider the generally avoided René Guénon as an historian of religions, we could refer the reader to some of his writings, where he expresses himself with the greatest precision (see for example the entire third part of Guénon 1952; or id. 1976: 69 ff., 87 ff., 105 ff.). The positions of a scholar like Giuseppe Tucci, at the same time an historicist and a structuralist, could, among the less attentive, give rise to some misunderstanding, but a statement such as the one that follows, confirms, in the negative, the point in question: "Before reaching this depletion, Indian philosophy, even if it was oppressed by the grave shadow of revelation, retarded by the cult of tradition, tripped up by its respect for everything that sounded like a venerable voice from the past, was not passed on inertly from one generation to the next" (Tucci 1977: 23)³.

Well then, how is it that the people who culturally belong to the tradition of the Old and New Testament, the Koran and the *Avesta* feel that the revelation of the Veda is so remote and incompatible with their own founding values? Why does it seem impossible to draw a comparison between the Veda and the other Books?⁴ There can only be one answer. The Veda, unlike the other Books which address, respectively, all the Jews, all the Westerners, and all the Muslims, certainly does not address, and did so even less in the past, all the Indians. And this is not because consistent sectors of Indian society rejected it (when this happened, the will and means to impose its norms were not lacking, as in Christianity and Islam: see below), but because it is the source of *varṇāśramadharmā*, the programmatic separateness between the social groups to which the Veda is revealed on one hand, and the many people who, not only in the facts, but also in principle, are denied to it. The "perennity" of the Veda is the perennity of a social order that does not allow for access to the revealed truth by a large part (by far the majority) of the population.

Since a social order naturally cannot be perennial, the word perennity should be properly understood. It is perfectly understood if we consider that the

³ In his *Storia della filosofia indiana*, from where the quoted passage is taken, Tucci shows himself to be a historicist and idealist by education and a structuralist by vocation. Indeed, his intention was "maybe for the first time, to expose the fundamental themes dealt with in the various schools; not, therefore, a history of them, particularly and singularly studied, but rather a discussion of the various modulations within them of certain central problems of the philosophical thought" (p. 3).

⁴ Staal (1983 b: 45) emphasizes the diversity (bordering on incongruity) of the texts that make up the Veda, which are really numerous, as the *Atharva Veda*, the *Brāhmaṇas*, the *Āraṇyakas* and the *Upaniṣads* have to be added to the three more ancient *saṃhitās*. But, on a lesser scale, even the Bible, rather than a Book, is a set of books that are often very different from each other; not to speak of the Koran, less stratified in time but containing extremely different material. That the Veda contains statements that are even opposing to each other had been noticed, as we have seen, by Manu himself. The point is not to raise (as far as we are concerned) problems of textual criticism, but to evaluate the way in which the respective Books were used by the priestly classes (or by the representatives of the faithful in Islam), how and why they were given their final form, and the extent to which the clergy succeeded in establishing a set of rules derived from them.

Brahmans, apart from having always claimed the religious and political leadership of the subcontinent⁵, have always managed (not without difficulty, as we shall see) to wield their power through the imposition of a social model which has remained the same in its general principles until very recently. Some scholars, like Romila Thapar, have strived to show everything that was change in ancient India, reacting to the profusion of theories and biased interest about an India "immemorial" that have been popular in the 19th and 20th centuries. In relation to the Brahmanic social model (which does *not* coincide with all that has been proposed on social order in India), we must underline the fact that *change has been functional in conservation*.

The claim of Manu (II, 14) that every twice-born man who treats the two sources of *dharma*, i.e. *śruti* and *smṛti*, with contempt "must be cast out by the virtuous, as an atheist and a scorner of the Veda" is perfectly comprehensible to those, for example the Christians, who have exemplarily hit (and, as long as it has been possible, annihilated) the heretics. The idea that divine revelation regards – how can we put it? – a limited number of people, is however not understood. In this, the Brahmanic community (and other social groups strictly associated to it) recalls the concept of the "chosen people" of the Hebrew tradition. In fact, while it is not difficult to convert to Christianity or Islam, it is by no means easy to become a Jew or a Brahman. In this parallel, the differences on an historical level are, naturally, enormous. The Brahmans, the "chosen people" by right of possessing the Veda, managed to impose their control over the various populations of the subcontinent, characterized by a lesser level of social and cultural complexity, and managed to maintain it through time, despite the dangerous internal threats (Buddhists and Jains) and the external ones (Islam, and, to a much lesser degree, the Westerners). Instead, the Jews, initially squashed between Egypt and Assyria-Babylonia, and later confronted with the Romans, Christianity and Islam (i.e. very developed systems) did not succeed in achieving their objective: the promised land (not theirs originally) was identified with a precise territory, which did not undergo, as did the Āryāvarta, a progressive geographic shifting: from the Punjab to the Upper Doab to Madhyadesa⁶.

A revealed book exists that founds a historical identity, and a conception, very remote in time (whatever the original beliefs expounded in the most ancient part of the Veda), of a Being from whom all manifestations (gods included) emanate, as does a chosen people which initially built its identity on an original revelation preserved in time through tradition. There is no reason not to use the

⁵ As we will see, the principle that political leadership had to be *naturaliter* a concern of the Kshatriyas was followed only until when they guaranteed the interests of the Brahmans. Just as the principle had been established by the latter, it was abandoned when conditions changed (save being reinstated in late Medieval times).

⁶ The gradually changing localization of the Āryāvarta documented in the texts (the reader is referred to Kane 1930–46, II, 1: 13 ff.) is confirmed by archaeological investigations. Bridget and Raymond Allchin (1982) have properly stressed the phenomenon.

term "religion" for a system founded and functioning in this manner, provided that we speak of "Brahmanic religion" and not of "Hindu religion", an expression lacking all sense. The aporia that it contains is perceived by Staal, who sidesteps it by affirming that to the east of Islam we face such a *saltus* that we must in any case renounce the term "religion", and must consider the Indian systems as functioning on bases that are completely different (memorable and rich in fallouts, even if only partly true, is the statement, repeated a number of times, that in the Asiatic systems ritual, conceived as invariant, comes first, then, very detached, mystic experience and, stone last, doctrine: see for example Staal 1985: 23 ff.). The solution proposed by Staal depends partly on the fact of not distinguishing between "Brahmanic religion" (which exists, at least in the same sense as a Jewish or Christian religion does) and "Hindu religion" (which does not exist at all, and most certainly did not in the past) clearly enough. This is a clear case of how the introduction of a particular word ("Hindu") complicates, rather than clarifies, the understanding of a phenomenon in search of definition, making it nebulous and incomprehensible. We could say, in this case, that *res sunt consequentia nominum*⁷. As we know, the term "Hinduism" was applied to India from the outside, unifying very different realities which the high segments of the Indian population would never have considered unified or capable of being unified (that is why the Veda sanctioned their diversity). To the Brahmins, the distance that separated them from the lower, or in any case different, segments of the population was no less than that which divided them from populations not living in India, or from the Muslims. Today, the term "Hindu" is not avoidable, and in a certain sense it is becoming even justifiable because of the enormous acceleration with which an increasing number of social groups have been aggregated into the Brahmanic driving force, and due to the birth of an Indian Republic based on the modern values of equality (historically extraneous to India). However, there is still ample means for observing what has been recalled here.

What Remained for the Jains

From within ancient Indian society, movements such as Buddhism and Jainism emerged, which succeeded in setting themselves up for a long time as autonomous and alternative social models to the Brahmanic one. They cannot actually be considered (at least up till a certain point and a certain period) as religions in the sense that we usually give to this term. They certainly do not have a Book as their foundation, nor did they have any priesthood in the past.

⁷ Another example of a word unknown to India, and one badly imposed from the exterior (in this case by scholars) is "Tantrism", which, also due to the reticence of many authors, has no comprehensible field of application and continues to create misunderstandings (see Verardi 1994: esp. 52-3).

In my opinion Buddhism was born as a Gnostic system, that is, as a dualistic anthroposophy, and did not simply develop, as maintained by Tucci in relation to "Tantric" Buddhism and by Conze to Mahāyāna (see Tucci 1949, I: 210 ff; II, 711, 730 ff; 1971: 345-7; Conze 1967) according to Gnostic lines. Buddhism, I believe *ab origine*, shares with Gnostic movements the persuasion that the world (actually, *this* world) is a place we must escape from, a world from which we feel estranged in the course of particular experience (the enlightenment). The salvation of man is not due to a transcendent intervention, but to *jñāna*, which, as Conze stressed (1967: 652), derives etymologically from the same Indo-European root as "gnosis". Typical of Gnostic conceptions is also the *deminutio*, if not the actual degradation, to which God or the gods are subjected. In Buddhism they are in fact reduced to a subordinate rank to that held by the Awakened One. The gods can do little else but recognize his superiority and render him homage. Buddhism was born in hard and direct struggle with the Brahmanic power. The opinion is widespread in the literature that, as in the texts of the Pāli Canon the Brahmins appear always to be treated with respect, the conflict could not be very strong. But the point is that such respect is not paid to all Brahmins, but only to those who are potential (and desired) allies of the antinomian revolt that Buddhism conducted. The escape from the world, of which the departure of Siddhārtha from Kapilavastu is the example, must be intended as an escape from the world controlled by the Brahmanic clergy. Indeed, the Buddha will choose the Middle Way, which rejects both the extreme forms of asceticism (a "no" to every possible form of world) and *this* world, oppressively controlled by Brahmanic *sacerdotium*. In the same way, the Gnostics took advantage of the politico-institutional crisis and the economic mutations in some regions of the ancient world, like Egypt, to challenge the traditional clergy*.

In India, the reaction against the clergy and the existing social order found support in the social groups representing urban realities and in the merchant world (we must remember that the latter's innovative mechanisms are disruptive when facing static and closed societies mainly based on the exploitation of land). The pertinence of the Buddhist revolution to this type of values and this social environment has been recognized for a long time, and I limit myself to referring

* See Green (1985: 49 ff.). I developed this discussion in a contribution I made at the congress on *Aspetti ellenistici-orientali della Tarda Antichità* held in Messina in September 1996, attempting to cast some light on both the typological similarities between the two movements and especially – a more important though more difficult thing because of the lack of material on Gnosticism – the historical ones. The similarities between the two systems, too precise to be accidental, can be explained, at least for the 1st and 2nd centuries A.D., if we consider that the Buddhist monasteries in Deccan and the Gnostic communities in the eastern Mediterranean controlled the sea trade between Rome and India. As is known, its amount had grown impressive by that time. For the whole question see Verardi (in the press b).

I thank Gherardo Gnoli, with whom I discussed at length the historical perspective in which movements like Buddhism, Jainism, and Gnosticism (including its Manichean version) should be placed.

to the analyses carried out firstly by Kosambi (1952: 191 ff.; 1965: 182–5, but *passim*; 1975: 266 ff.), further investigated by Thapar (e.g. 1978: 40 ff.; 63 ff.; 122 ff.) and spread by other authors (e.g. Gokhale 1977: 127 ff.; 1982). We will see more clearly below how movements like Buddhism formed a grave, ir retrievable split in the Indo-Aryan élite, which, since the 5th–4th centuries B.C., had been represented on one hand, on the political level, by the urbanised Kshatriyas legitimated by Buddhism to accumulate and invest wealth (Thapar 1995: 119), and, on the other, by the Brahmans and those Kshatriyas who had remained faithful to them, hostile to urban life and bound to the traditional possession of land.

From the point of view of its position towards society, Buddhism was born as a group of *Electi* (which remained such through the mutations, even the more relevant, that it underwent: from the *āryasamgha* to the Bodhisattvas or incarnated, etc.), rather remote from the larger population – with the exception, in the early times, and often also during the later period, of the social groups mentioned above (in Kausambi during the 10th–12th centuries there was still a considerable number of merchants who professed Buddhism: see Mazumdar 1956: 175; in Medieval Bengal there were still merchants who refused to abandon Buddhism: see Vedāntasāstri 1956: 73) – to which not much attention was paid, left as it was to its customs and useless cults.

A revealed truth is not, and cannot be, the foundation of Buddhism; this is, rather, a teaching aimed at gnosis. Even a teaching (consider that of Christ) can be understood and passed on as a revealed truth, but Buddhism did not lend itself to this interpretation. The concept of truth cannot but have as its basis the concept of Being, but Buddhism, according to an opinion that I share, lacks an ontology⁹, and does not allow any anchorage to the emerging of a revelation (from where should it come?).

For our discussion it is not necessary for these opinions on Buddhism to be shared *in toto*. The important point to consider is that for some time (with Aśoka) Buddhism acquired a decisive political, institutional and economic dimension *making a clean break from the Veda and with all that it represented from the point of view of tradition, political power and social institutions*. Serious misunderstandings have arisen over this question. One thing is to reaffirm that the roots of Buddhism are found in the Indian tradition, and in the Upanishadic tradition in particular as, among others, Staal has done (1985: 37 ff.; I do not

⁹ See the argument made by Bharati (1977: esp. 18 ff.), who analyses Mahāyāna and Vajrayāna Buddhism, i.e. that which in the histories of philosophy (because of the cultural conditioning that Bharati denounces: see in particular note 18 at p. 32) is thought to have attributed to *nirvāṇa* characters that would make it similar to the *brahman* of the Vedānta and to the *ātman*, transcendent and motionless, of the Upanishads. As regards the concept of *nirvāṇa* in the Pāli Canon, it is very distant from that of Being in the Brahmanic tradition. Lanotte (1958: 44 ff.), after taking into account the discussion on the subject, could do little else but conclude, quoting the *Visuddhimagga*, that *nirvāṇa* is, but whoever enters it is not.

agree, however, when he maintains "qu'il est difficile de distinguer entre les idées bouddhiques et celles des Upanishad": id. 1990: 26); another is to conclude that, because of this fact, Buddhism has never been an autonomous system in India (its ascetic model, and therefore its social representativeness, turned definitely away from that of the Upanishads, basically monistic and largely brahmanized; see Verardi: in the press b). It is not possible for me to agree with the apparent demonstration of Staal's assumption, which consists of identifying an essentially ritualistic system in Buddhism, which as such – given the permanence of rituals and the impermanence of the rest (Staal 1985: 27 ff.; 1986: 206–7) – cannot greatly differentiate itself from the other systems. We will see how the analysis of historical events, even if necessarily very brief here, displays that the terms of the question are very different, and tragically complicated.

I would also like to underline how the positions that I have recalled are, basically, those of modern Brahmanism, which for a long time has been engaged in a "cultural" and "national" recovery of Buddhism, supporting the idea of its contiguity with the orthodox tradition. Recovery, that is, by weakening. This was the position of a Coomaraswamy, and then of many other scholars, even the more lay and sceptical, who, very often being unaware, moved and are moving within the Brahmanic model of interpretation of the history of ancient India. The Brahmanic religion, for which the concept of truth is certainly not marginal as in most sectors of modern epistemology, but central, and centered in the Veda, did not historically tolerate the existence of alternative systems to its own. The idea of the decadence of Buddhism in India for internal reasons, and of its "reabsorption" into the Vedic-"Hindu" system from which it originated, is false, and is functional in strengthening the power of hegemonic type of the Brahmins and of the Brahmanic ideology which took shape at the end of the last century and has quickened after Indian independence. The numerous histories of India that have followed one another in this century are generally mystifying in this regard and more so as we approach modern times (below).

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Before considering the very serious dissent that opposed Brahmins and Buddhists, and the final defeat of the latter, I would like to draw attention to some aspects of the history of Jainism, a system, in ancient times, that was similar to Buddhism in many respects, and certainly in the fact that it shared Gnostic characteristics. It is useful to do so because Jainism has survived in India and we know a great deal about its later revealing events, and because there is sufficient material in its history to demonstrate the partial fallacy of Staal's theory of ritual.

In the Jain tradition, the awareness is very much alive that the movement was supported from the outset (and afterwards up till the Middle Ages) by Kshatriya lineages engaged, as states Jaini (1979: 275), in a constant fight against the claims to supremacy of the Brahman class. The Śvetāmbara tradition of the transfer of the embryo of Mahāvīra from the original womb of the Brahman Devānandā to that of the Kshatriya woman Trīśālā could not be more revealing.

The myth (a transparent one) displays the precise choice of Mahāvīra of not identifying himself with the Brahmanic model of society. His choice deserves even more consideration because it discloses the fact that even a part of the Brahmans adhered to what, simplifying somewhat, and recalling for certain aspects the long-outdated views of Garbe (1903), may be called the "Kshatriya model". But we know that this effectively happened from the history of ancient Buddhism as well (see Gokhale 1980).

With the Brahmanic reorganization first attempted in the Śuṅga period, and attained for the first time only with the Guptas, it was above all Vishnuism that succeeded in adapting the principles of the Veda to modern reality, finally imposing itself, not without difficulty, as the modern depository of orthodoxy¹⁰. The reaction to systems that were authentically alternative, which contested the Veda and therefore the principle of authority and legitimacy of the Brahmans, became violent. It was in the Vishnuite milieu (in a period that is difficult, but not impossible, to specify) that the myth of Rāma in its orthodox version (see Thapar 1987: 14) and that – clearly of Brahmanic origin – of Paraśurāma, the exterminators of the Kshatriyas, were formed, which we will consider below.

In the South, the conflict featured first the Sivaïtes marshalled on the orthodox front. The events regarding Jainism which took place in the Andhra country and in Tamil Nadu are relatively well-known. The "Kshatriya model" of society had successfully imposed itself there¹¹, probably favoured by the social and economic motor made up of the complex mercantile network favoured, since the times of the Republic, by Rome, and typically developed in the urban centres¹². Contrary to the norm, according to which the Brahman class would conceal the

¹⁰ The interest in the politics followed by the Śuṅgas on the ideological and religious level rests on the fact that for the first time we find the Vedic orthodox tradition (Puśyamitra, as we know from the inscription of Ayodhya, carried out the *aśvamedha* twice – see Sircar 1965: 94–5 – in opposition to the model of kingship and state attempted by Aśoka) joined to the beginning of the iconographic and monumental tradition promoted by currents that Vishnuism will later make its own. See the temple and the pillars crowned by the emblems of the *pañcavīras* in Besnagar, one of the Śuṅga capitals, erected to rival the Buddhist centre of Sanchi nearby, probably the object of destruction in that time (below); for the temple of Besnagar, see Khare (1967); on the cult of the *pañcavīras*, considered independent from Vishnuism, see Härtel (1987). For the Guptas, see below.

¹¹ One of the criteria adopted by modern antiquarians to spot Jain vestiges in Deccan, was to head directly for the ancient local capitals (see Murthy 1963: 36–7).

¹² One of the most singular finds in the excavation of Jean-Marie Casal at Virampatnam–Arikamedu of 1947–8 are semi-finished condyles of bovines, the finished correspondents of which are documented in a 2nd century B.C. level under the Casa dei Grifi on the Palatine (Casal 1949: 29). A more careful study of the Mediterranean amphoras which came to light in the site excavated by Wheeler (1946) has shown that they are, partly (those for wine) a product of the Bay of Naples from the 2nd century B.C. onwards and that "Greek and Roman traders were, even in the Republican period, aware that Indian exports such as precious woods, animals, spices, oils, perfumes, ivory, gems, and rock crystals could be obtained more directly and probably more cheaply by sea than by the arduous and costly overland trade routes" (Will 1991: 154). Also Warner Slane (1991) maintains that the Koan amphoras found at Arikamedu date partly to the 1st century B.C., and that "if the trade between Rome and India is primarily of the first century A.D., especially the first half", there are "suggestions of contact in the later first century B.C. and in the early second century"

signs of the political and social dissent with the utmost care, and therefore history, by means of that "control of oblivion" which Jacques Le Goff maintains has always been one of the most ruthless instruments of power, we know that in Tamil Nadu the violent reaction against Jainism by the Nāyanmārs first, and then the Ālvārs, forced the surviving Jains to move away to Karnataka, where there were still Kshatriya lineages, like the Gaṅgas, who were prepared to support them (see Pusalker in Majumdar 1964: 292). The violence of the anti-Jain preaching by the Sivaite saints Sambandar and Appar (a convert) in the 7th century and, more significantly, the Brahmanic pressure on the Kshatriya lineages that the Jains represented on an ideological level (whence conversions and persecutions), is well-known. The most famous of them are those of Kūṅ Pāṇḍya (identified with Arikesari Māravarnam), who, at Madurai, converted and instigated by Sambandar, ordered the massacre by impalement of eight thousand Jains (an event that to this day is revived in an *utsava*: see T.A.G. Rao 1914-6, I: 55-6) and of Mahendrarman I further north, in the Pallava territory, who was responsible for the destruction of the Jain temple of Punavati and the killing by torture of a great number of Jains in nearby Tiruvattur (formerly one of the principal towns of the Jains), who "were destroyed by being hanged, cut to pieces, and crushed in oil mills", as represented by sculptures on the walls of the local temple (Sewell 1882: 167; here see fig. 1). Apart from being documented in texts that are linguistically inaccessible to me, like the *Periyapurāṇam*¹³, the persecutions are – and this is a truly exceptional fact in India – testified in the iconography, which kept the memory of the events alive at least until the last century.

One of the reliefs in Tiruvattur (south of Vellore) depicts a Jain hanging face-down on a sharpened pole which pierces him and exit from his back, while a wild pig begins to feed off him (fig. 2). In another, two heretics are forced to sit on the horizontal bar that separates the trunk of the pole from its point, and are likewise bitten by pigs (fig. 3). The same torture (without the presence of the wild pigs) is represented in a relief on the basement of the temple of Melakkadambur (south of Cuddalore), being the final scene of the ordeal of the sacred texts in the Vaigai river (fig. 4)¹⁴. In a panel of the frieze of the *maṇḍapa*

(p. 212). This position is shared, on the basis of independent evidence, by De Romanis, the author of an up-to-date study on Indo-Roman trade. According to him, its continuous but slow growth from the end of the 2nd century to ca. 30 B.C. was followed by a sudden, stunning acceleration (see De Romanis 1996: 157 ff., 167 ff.).

¹³ Vincent Smith, in *The Early History of India*, one of the few history texts where space has been given to the theme of the persecutions (even if somewhat minimized), refers particularly to the 62nd and 63rd Tiruvallīadai in the set of manuscripts collected by Colonel Colin Mackenzie, of which H.H. Wilson gave a *Descriptive Catalogue* published in Calcutta in 1828 and reprinted in Madras in 1882 (H.V.).

¹⁴ Thrown into the river, the Sivaite manuscripts sailed upstream, while the Jain ones were swept away. The ordeal was called for and organized by Sambandar, supported in particular by the minister Kulaccirai (later made a saint, *nāyanmār*). The similarities to our Medieval history are irresistible.

B of the temple of Śiva at Darasuram the ordeal is depicted on the left, while on the right four impaled Jains appear (L'Herneault 1987: 101 and photo 22). It is interesting, even if distressful, to see both forms of impalement perpetuated (fig. 5) in a painting from the 17th century on the inner wall of the gateway to the Tiruppudaimarudur temple (to the northwest of Palayankottai). On the ceiling of a hall at Avudayarkovil, close to Tanjore, the last of the painted scenes of the ordeal, dating to the 18th century (fig. 6), shows the Jain ascetics clearly, naked and hairy, impaled and prey to the pigs and crows. The inscription reads:

Kulaccēra nayiṅār kaḷu pāṭupaṭac colli camaṅarkaḷai kaḷup pōṭṭaviṭam
(The place where the *nāyanmār* Kulaccirai [minister of Kūṅ Pāṇḍya] ordered that the Jains be impaled)¹⁵.

In a sub-shrine of the same temple, a painting with the same subject matter on the outer wall, dating to the 19th century (fig. 7), shows a variant of the torment. The poles here lack the horizontal bar, and pierce the ascetics from below, exiting at the top of the head. The legend on the left reads:

Campanta cuvāmikaḷ vai
kaḷiyiliṭṭa ēṭu etir
[nō]kkic cenṛatu
(The manuscript placed in the Vaigai by Sambandar sailed against the current).

The legend of the scene on the right reads:

camaṅarkaḷai kaḷu
vēṭṭiyatu
(The Jains were impaled).

As to the murals in the Mīnākṣī temple in Madurai depicting the torments of the Jains, they were noticed by Saleore (1938: 279) many years ago.

M.S. Ramaswami Ayyangar, one of those scholars of a few generations ago who did not overlook the facts and did not minimize them, stressed the fact that the Āḷvārs completed the persecution and annihilation of the Jains, so that between the 9th and 10th centuries the Jains lost any prominence in the land (Ayyangar 1922: esp. 59–72). B. Seshagiri Rao, in analyzing the events of Jain history in Andhradesa and Karnataka, observed on his part that the “extraordinary phenomenon” of the persecutions against Jainism deserved “explanation on some hypothesis other than the *merely* revivalistic zeal of the followers of the *Vaidica*, which is, for this period, the *Pauranica Dharma*. But such persecutions paved the way for social reverses very often recorded in the traditions of the Andhra–Karnata villages, leading ultimately to the all but complete obscuration of all traces of Jainism in the Andhra–Karnata country” (B.S. Rao 1922: 31).

¹⁵ This and the following legends have been transcribed and translated for me by my colleague in the Istituto Universitario Orientale (Dipartimento di Studi Asiatici) Professor Gabriella Eichinger Ferro-Luzzi, whom I thank. In this first legend there are numerous colloquial spellings (e.g. *camaṅar* instead of *camaṅar*; *kaḷu* instead of *kaḷu*; etc.).

Here we are faced with the violent substitution of a social and political model with a new one supported by new pro-brahmanic lineages which came about in ways that reveal, according to the same author, whom I believe I am interpreting correctly, that the *historical Brahmanic tradition appears to be indistinct because of its interest in cancelling the traces of the historical discontinuities which reveal weaknesses and crises of the Brahmanic model and instead reaffirm the principle of an uninterrupted hegemony*. If similar "social reverses" were recorded so often in the villages of Deccan, it is evident that the facts that we are recalling were not episodic, as claimed by all conventional historiography, but amounted to a radical "cleansing" – certainly one of the largest (if we consider that this also happened to the Buddhists: see below) that history records.

Nor did the Jains survive (apart from a small minority) because of having accepted humiliating (but forced) compromises with Brahmanism. This is an extremely interesting point for our discussion. Indeed, in order to survive, they resorted to a sort of mimicry of the Brahman institutions and behaviours, that if, on one hand, assured them their survival, caused their weakening and the almost total loss of their identity. Jināsena, in the 8th century (towards the end of which, referring to the most commonly accepted chronology, that Śaṅkara appeared, who was the greatest apostle of orthodoxy and persecutor of heretics), incorporated the sixteen *saṃskāras* of the Brahmans into the Jain system "almost in their entirety, becoming part of a larger list of fifty-three *kriyas* (actions) which marked all the important events of life" (Jaini 1979: 293). A "class of 'Jaina brahmans'" was introduced among the Digambaras, entrusted with the care of the temples and the performance of elaborate rituals" (ib.: 291), that could appear, in virtue of the consequent acceptance of the Brahmanic bias against the *sūdras* (ib.: 294) and of the concept of "twice-born" (ib.: 289–90) – in one word, of the caste system – as one of the different *internal* subdivisions of the Brahmanic authority, and not as an élite which opposed it. The forced adjustment of Jainism to the Brahmanism of the *bhakti* should also be considered, that is, the acceptance of most Brahmanic divinities and of amended versions of the *Mahābhārata* and the *Rāmāyaṇa* (the most important texts of the triumphant Vishnuite ideology: cf. ib.: 304–5; for the *Rāmāyaṇa* of the Jains see however Thapar 1987: 14–5). Had Jain teachers ignored these texts – Jaini comments – "they would have done so at the peril of their own society's disintegration" (Jaini 1979: 304). Only on these terms were the Jains allowed to survive as a community. From the Brahmanic point of view, the Jina could be described (this is usual stuff) as the Universal Spirit who is Śiva, Dhātṛ, Sugata (i.e., the likewise neutralized Buddha), and Viṣṇu (cf. Pusalker, in Majumdar 1964: 296).

The point seems clear: the Brahmans only came to accept the Jains at the moment in which, already deprived of their political power because of heavy persecutions, they were forced, even if unable to accept the Veda (from which, for at least one aspect, they were less distant than the Buddhists because of their belief in *ātman*), to accept the *varṇāśramadharmā* which comes down from it. To Brahmanic eyes this was the same, in the facts, as the acceptance of the Veda itself. It is only at this point that the doctrinal differences between the two

systems could be considered marginal with respect to an "anthropologically" observed reality and, to repeat one of the most famous (and in a certain sense most useful) claims by Staal, that orthodoxy becomes a far less important concept than orthopraxis (Staal 1983 a: 6; 1990 a: 8; on orthodoxy, see below). The reaction of the Jains to this state of enslavement was only possible when the odd man out, Islam¹⁶, arrived on the Indian scene, becoming (it is still so today) the new, true obstacle to the establishment of a complete Brahmanic hegemony.

To come to the point that interests us most here, i.e. Staal's positions on rituals, we must ask ourselves the question: are there rituals that exist in themselves, self-justified, only explained *ex post* in a different manner (in the case observed here) by Brahmanic doctrine from one side and by Jain doctrine on the other, or rather, Brahmanic and neo-Brahmanic ("Hindu") rituals imposed by force on another system which accepted them because it would otherwise have run the risk of dying out? Speculation and doctrine were what remained to them after being barred from what really counts, i.e. political power and the ownership of land. Is it really true that rituals precede doctrine *in any case*, and not instead that they have been imposed from the outside on a system that has only doctrinal matters as a way of differentiating and surviving? It seems to me that, in truth, things are so much this way that there is at least a Brahmanic ritual (but one of the most important, the *śrāddha*) to which the Jains would not submit, as the *total* loss of their identity was at stake (Jaini 1979: 302–4). The doctrine could not be further denied, as it was considered as the last bulwark of defence.

Things had gone differently, from the very first establishing of Brahmanic authority in India, with less developed and sophisticated systems than that of the Jains. Imprisoning them, when necessary, in the Brahmanic model, had never encountered (as far as we know) major obstacles. Leaving them to themselves, when possible (as in the less sought-after territories: see the various groups of "Tribals" still nowadays), was not threatening. In any case, they were systems that had arisen outside the Indo-Aryan élite and were foreign to it – very different, therefore, from Jainism and Buddhism, which testify to a dramatic vertical split in that élite.

The Brahmins and the Buddhists

Coming now to Buddhism, the question is rather complicated, because it was a phenomenon of even greater importance than that, more noteworthy than we are led to believe today, of Jainism (which was hegemonic in many parts of Deccan and Western India for a long time), because its repression was total (with the only, partial exception of the Valley of Kathmandu, which we will speak about), and because its

¹⁶ It can be interesting to recall that, in the 16th century, Abū'l Faẓl 'Allāmī observed that "The Brahmins deem it better to face a raging elephant or a ravenous lion than to meet with one of this [the Jains'] sect" ('Allāmī 1927–49. III: 222).

oblivion was complete¹⁷. It is arduous to make the real ways of its disappearance emerge, as they depend on an evidence which is often badly known, badly evaluated and minimized in modern literature, which is Brahmanic or Western. In the 19th century, the fact that Buddhism had been cancelled from Indian history by the Brahmins was currently recognized. Sir Walter Elliot did not hesitate to speak of 'extirpation' and 'extermination' of the Buddhists (Elliot 1885: 92, 126). A famous scholar like Gopinatha Rao recalled, for example, that in Travancore "The belief among the teachers of history in our schools and colleges is that Buddhism died in the land of its birth not long after its birth, and that the Brahmins killed it and drove away all its followers" (T.A.G. Rao 1920: 123). Like all of the Brahmanic intelligentsia after him, he was, however, quick to embrace the thesis, upheld particularly by the Westerners (he recalls Hendrik Kern; *ib.*: 10), according to which "the downfall of Buddhism is due to Muhammadans". The more easily Islam lent (and lends) itself to the function of scapegoat for past behaviours that are unjustifiable in the light of the idea that modern "Hinduism" desired (and desires) to give of itself as the one and only religion of a superior tolerance and spirituality, the more it was (and is) considered by the Brahmanic power as the true, modern obstacle to its total hegemony¹⁸. The idea of a "tolerant" India in the politico-religious field is still so widespread, despite the continual proof to the contrary, that even the brighter and more critical western scholars are at a loss to evaluate the question. Only Thapar (1987: 15) has clearly stated that the religious tolerance and non-violence attributed to Hinduism is not borne out by evidence, maintaining that the persecution against the Buddhists and Jains is "a major historical problem which requires detailed investigation" (*ib.*: 18).

It was the very influential T.W. Rhys Davids who established what was later almost always maintained. A short note of 1896 ended like this:

¹⁷ It is easily forgotten that familiar places like Sanchi, Sarnath and the Deccan caves were lost to memory until they were discovered, by Westerners, during the last century. No trace had remained of the Buddhist institutions, except what was preserved, in the negative, in the oral tradition. The same cannot be said of ancient Brahmanic monuments, the loss of which is rather due (as in Christianity) to changes in the cult, to the decline of certain areas in favour of others, etc. (in Northern India the Muslim factor was, clearly, very important in later times).

¹⁸ According to the Indian variant of what is "politically correct", it is generally not admitted that this opinion is amply shared by sectors of Hindu public opinion that do not support political parties of a fundamentalist orientation, and that it has always been prevalent also among the supporters of the Congress Party of the Nehru-Gandhis. That the Muslims represent an intolerable *vulnus* to the Brahmins is naturally explicit in fundamentalist milieus. K. Elst (1991), a convert, circumstantially attacks any pretence at legitimacy of their presence in India. It is significant how he also denies the existence of anti-Buddhist persecutions: "In the case of their purely concocted grand theory of pre-Muslim persecution of Buddhism by Hindus, we see our leftist historians throw all standards of source criticism to the wind" (p. 87); Brahmin oppression, Buddhism as a social reform movement, the Buddhist-Brahmin power struggle are all "myths" (cf. p. 116); but "Once this Marxist-inspired myth of Buddhism and Jainism as social reform movements gets debunked, the authority of those who publicly identify with this myth will also be questioned" (*ib.*). A large number of publications have been available in India for a long time which have been ignored by Western scholars, mostly of lay training and unwilling to take them into consideration (many years ago I reported about some examples: see Verardi 1977). They are fed by inexistent issues but involve a (comparatively) large part of the intelligentsia. In note 30 (below) scientific contributions relative to the question of the historicity of Rāma are recalled, which fall within this framework.

"(...) the adherents of faiths logically so diametrically opposed lived side by side for a thousand years in profound peace. It is a phenomenon most striking to the Western historian, who will not refuse to recognize, as one continuing factor, the memory of the marvellous tolerance of the great Buddhist emperor Asoka. But this tolerance itself rests on anterior causes. It must be reckoned to the credit of the Indian people as a whole; and it is evidence of the wide spread, in the valley of the Ganges, during the centuries before Asoka, of a higher level of enlightenment and culture than has, I venture to think, been hitherto sufficiently recognised in the West" (Rhys Davids 1896: 92).

A century later it is easy to observe that at the basis of these claims lies a precise cultural conditioning: *exoticism*. India is the place of a religious tolerance that is inexistent elsewhere (Mrs Rhys Davids, a few lines above the cited passage, recalled "the persecutions which the reforming Christians have had to suffer at the hands of the orthodox Church"; could she have been thinking of the Latimers, the Riddleys and the Cranmers commemorated in Broad Street at Oxford?). Exoticism (which, in my opinion, is implicitly present in the positions of Staal when he claims the radical diversity that, beyond the Khyber, manifests itself in the religious field *in all cases*) was matched, in Rhys Davids, by a great competence, and precisely in the field of Buddhist studies. If it was she who denied the persecutions against Buddhism, could things have happened in some other way? Positions such as hers determined the end of investigations that in reality had never been started. This was favoured by the increasingly strong presence of westernized Indians struggling for political freedom in the field of academic studies. They transformed an assumption based on exoticism into one of the principal ideological elements that made up the image of the new India, a founding factor of its internal and international identity¹⁹. That certain facts never, and could never have, happened in India has become axiomatic, the first premise of a syllogism that in its conclusion goes as far as to turn the facts upside down. Here is a brief passage from the second volume of *A Comprehensive History of India* relative, as was that by Rhys Davids, to the events of the time of Puṣyamitra Śuṅga:

"In view of the fact that religious persecution in ancient India was an exception rather than the rule, and keeping in mind the tendency of the Buddhist writers to distort facts and invent imaginary accounts of the evil deeds of non Buddhists – even Aśoka has not been spared – we cannot give the same credence to these accounts as has been accorded by some writers. While it may be conceded that some Buddhists, particularly the monks, may have suffered from certain disabilities, the story of a general persecution of all and sundry is evidently the invention of frustrated minds which found that the state patronage was rapidly being shifted to Brahmins, and were aghast at the revival of the ancient Vedic ritual of the *aśvamedha*. It is not even unlikely that the hardships of the Buddhists were in many cases due to political reasons and were of their own inviting" (K.A.N. Sastri 1957: 99).

The few contributions by Buddhists to the discussion (e.g. Alahakoon 1984: 205 ff.) can do little else but fall into the void, if for nothing else, because they

¹⁹ Hence, along with considering Aśoka in his exclusive role as sovereign of a large empire, the choice of the Sarnath capital as the emblem of the new Republic. As Rhys Davids absurdly maintained, had not Aśoka (a perfect stranger, by the way, to the Indians until the mid-19th century) displayed a "marvellous tolerance"?

are suspect of animosity. Here, it is not even possible to touch upon the facts which have been known for a long time, and I limit myself to referring to the works of R.C. Mitra (1981), who incarnates and synthetizes the current Brahmanic and Western positions, and of Hazra (1995) who, while generally accepting the traditional views, admits that the Brahmanical hostility towards Buddhism was one of the causes of the decadence of Buddhism (see especially pp. 385 ff.). It is preferable, I believe, to underline the emergence of new or little-known facts, which sooner or later will certainly push for the re-examination of the entire question. Many of them come from a particular sector of the research, archaeology and art history.

The first fact, not yet fully evaluated for its importance, regards the datings which have been current for some time now of the most important Buddhist monuments built after the Mauryans. Today it is clear, for example, that no Buddhist monument goes back to the height of the Śuṅga period, and that, in any case, they have nothing to do with royal patronage, which was aimed at the traditional, solemn rituals that were reaffirmative of the Brahmanic conception of kingship like the *aśvamedha*²⁰. The patronage of the stone railing of the stūpa at Bharhut was only possible towards the end of the Śuṅga dominion, when the project of a politico-religious restoration by Puśyamitra and Agnimitra had by then failed, the dynasty was on the brink of collapse, and the local feudatories could no longer resist and, if ever, had to favour – in order to hold on – the power of the monasteries, which were crucial allies of non-agrarian interests. Bharhut was situated along the trade route that joined western Deccan with Madhyadesa via Vidisa and was certainly – I follow a suggestion of Max Weber's (1993: 200) – one of the stations that held the monopoly over storage and roads, maximizing the effects of trade that otherwise, given its relatively small dimensions, would not have managed to pay the costs of the construction and maintenance of the infrastructures. The same can be said for the resuming of the building activity at Sanchi, for which I believe we should follow Marshall in maintaining that it is very likely that the sacred area of the Mauryan period had been sacked and semi-destroyed by the anti-Buddhist reaction carried out by Puśyamitra (Marshall – Foucher 1940: 23–4)²¹. Only in around 100 B.C. did the conditions for the restoration of stūpa 1 and the patronage of the *vedikā* of stūpa 2 occur.

²⁰ In note 10 we have referred to Puśyamitra as an *aśvamedhin* king. Contemporary historiography has generally forgotten the political meaning of this solemn ritual because it has no interest in interpreting it – from the Mauryan period onwards – as an orthodox, anti-*śramaṇa* manifesto. Today, it is rare for scholars to investigate in this direction. S.P. Gupta (1980: 215) has however suggested a date for the caves of the Ājivikas in the Barabar hills on the basis of the dramatic political upheaval that took place when Puśyamitra gained power with a coup. To scholars of some generations ago, like K.P. Jayaswal (aiming instead, in colonial India, at reinstating Hindu identity) Buddhism appeared, not entirely incorrectly, as an essentially anti-national movement, which not only the Śuṅgas, but many other dynasties opposed. See his extraordinary book, *History of India. 150 A.D. to 350 A.D.* (Jnyaswal 1933), substantially based on the identification and glorification of the national anti-Kuṣāṇa and anti-Buddhist dynasties led by *aśvamedhin* kings.

²¹ With regard to stūpa 1, Marshall observed that the great damage suffered by the original

The patronage of the early Buddhist caves in Western Deccan, none of which are today dated to earlier than 100 B.C.²², was due to the artisans, traders, small landowners and officers supported by the Śaka-Kṣatrapas, and as for – to cite an important later example – the second phase of Ajanta (the most famous and celebrated), today it is ascribed to the years 462–77, due as it was to the Buddhist sovereign Hariṣeṇa of the Vākāṭaka house, the whole project being dropped when he died. The studies on the subject by Walter Spink (1972; 1975; 1981; 1991; 1992 and numerous others), analytic and exhaustive, have focussed on the question of the patronage, supplying an example of how it is possible to abandon the equivocal indeterminateness according to which Indian political power, and only that, was also well disposed towards its toughest adversaries (I am sorry to say it, but the historians of ancient India seem to move between Metastasio and Candide).

The Buddhist images for which Gupta art has long been famous go back either (a few of them) to the times of the last imperial crisis, or to the period following the collapse of the dynasty (Verardi, in the press a), when all the anti-Brahmanic forces which the orthodox restoration of the 4th century had put

structure of burnt brick “could not have been due to mere weathering, but must have been wantonly inflicted” (p. 23). However, he attributed the restorations to representatives of the Śuṅga dynasty itself, Agnimitra or Vasuṣeṣṭha (pp. 29, 36). But, starting from the article by Walter Spink of 1958, all the dating of Sanchī has been brought down of a few decades (all scholars are agreed now on dating the gateways of stūpa 1 to the first decades of the 1st century A.D., and not to the last decades of the 1st century B.C., as Marshall did), so that also the dating of the phase of restoration following that of destruction must be lowered to not earlier than the year 100 B.C. The resuming of the building activity at Sanchī can be ascribed to a patronage made possible within the framework of the new Indian political order determined by the presence of the Western Kṣatrapas and of the Śakas.

The revision of the chronology of the earlier Buddhist monuments which has been carried out during the last 20–30 years (see the following note) contributes to disrupting the nationalist outline of an otherwise serious and reliable scholar such as Debala Mitra, turned perfectly upside-down with respect to the real dynamics of the facts, which will become gradually clearer as the exposition proceeds. I quote from her guidebook of the Archaeological Survey of India (D. Mitra 1965: 6–8): “After a temporary setback following the break-up of the Mauryan empire... The religious fervour found its expression in a vigorous building activity about the middle of the second century B.C., during which the Śuṅgas were ruling... The establishment of a foreign power in the Malwa region under the Kṣatrapas, engaged in chronic warfare, hardly provided any incentive for the dormant workshop... After a prolonged period of stagnation and lassitude under the Kṣatrapas, there was a revival of sculptural activity during the reign of the Guptas, who... Provided peace and prosperity essential for the growth of artistic pursuits”. The monuments of Sanchī here appear to be the exclusive work of the “national” dynasties.

²² These are dates that, having been proposed by pioneer scholars for some time, have now been accepted in general works. In Härtel & Auboyer (1971), for example, stūpa 2 at Sanchī is dated to about 100 B.C., Bharhut between 125 and 75 B.C. (p. 162), Pīṭalkhōra to ca. 100 B.C. (p. 160), and Bhaja to the 1st century B.C.; in Huntington (1985), Sanchī 2 is dated to 100 B.C. (p. 62), Bharhut to 100–80 B.C. (p. 65), Kondivite to ca. 100 B.C., and Bhaja to 100–70 B.C. (p. 75). The authors who suggest or accept these dates, which are so late with respect to earlier assumptions (Coomaraswamy, to cite but one example, in his *History of Indian and Indonesian Art* of 1927 considered Bharhut to date to about 150 B.C. [p. 31], the *vihāra* of Bhaja an early Śuṅga monument [pp. 24, 230], Bedsa, Kondane and Pīṭalkhōra as dating back to ca. 175 B.C. [pp. 28, 230]; etc.), are not always able, however, to define the historical framework with accuracy.

out of action, peremptorily resurfaced. A Gupta Buddhist art does not exist (as, instead, Sir John Marshall pretended), and reasonably so, given that the Guptas, expression of the most rigid Brahmanic interests, took up, on the political level, the conquest and organization of the territories that had escaped Brahmanic control for a long time and, on the religious and institutional level, the re-establishment of the great Vedic rituals and, occasionally, the patronage of the neo-orthodox Vishnuite iconism²³.

There is clear evidence of deliberate destruction of Buddhist monuments from many excavations (even if most of them, besides being insufficiently checked, have been carried out with the aim of establishing a national ideology). I recalled elsewhere (ib.) the examples of Sravasti and Kathmandu, which provide evidence, as is very often the case in the North, of a violent opposition of Vishnuite origin to Buddhism. The case of Kathmandu is particularly significant because it has recently emerged from controlled excavations carried out at Harigaon (Verardi 1992) and because it reveals the radical destruction, in about A.D. 800, of a sacred Buddhist area, which was carried out along with the construction of a temple in its place dedicated to Satya Nārāyaṇa and with an anti-Buddhist inscription on a *Garudastamba* (one of the major epigraphic texts from Medieval India; see it in Gnoli 1956: 14–7), the excavation shedding important light on this very text. In it, Vyāsa, the ṛṣi who explains the Veda and is the supposed author of the *Mahābhārata*, is praised for being a resolute opposer of Buddhist heresy. Without his intervention, the followers of Sugata who had enticed the people by false arguments, with evil designs, would have managed to lead the world astray (Verardi 1992: 23 ff., 69 ff., 88 ff.). What had seemed to scholars to be a dispute carried out on the level of debate, was revealed to be the sign of a violent anti-Buddhist reaction²⁴.

In the third phase of the sequence at the site of Antichak in Bihar, identified with Vikramasīla, the Buddhist images were re-employed as building materials by the Senas, a dynasty well-known for its orthodoxy (they called themselves Karnata-Kshatriyas, Brahma-Kshatriyas or Kshatriyas *tout court* – see Ganguly in Majumdar 1966: 35 –, that is, Kshatriyas who declared themselves loyal to the Brahmins). Radhakrishna Chaudhary, who evidenced this fact (besides which we can recall yet another, and that is that the Brahmanic images which have been

²³ In the same place that had seen the beginning of Bhagavatism, that is, Vidisa, we owe to the entourage of Candragupta II, successor of *aśvamedhin* sovereigns who had conceded nothing to the innovative Brahmins, the first great manifesto of Vishnuite iconography (beginning of the 5th century) – the Varāha cave at Udayagiri (on which see the accurate iconographic description by D. Mitra 1963, the acute observations on its historical-ideological meaning by Sohoni 1971, and the considerations of Williams 1982: 43–6).

²⁴ Wiesner (1980) has shown that all the stūpas of Kathmandu were deprived of the images in the niches, and considered as *liṅgas*, and has expressed opinions that do not differ, even if limited to the specific object of his research, from those expressed in these pages. The stūpas that today would be considered as having been the object of uninterrupted worship have, in reality, been reactivated in recent times.

found are fairly intact; see Narayan 1977–8: 214) in a very thorough article, is one of the few authors who recognize that “an element of hatred and vengeance seem to be prominent in the minds of the builders against Buddhism”, and that “*Religious rivalry was one of the fundamental causes of the destruction of the University*” (emphasis by Chaudhary 1978: 229–30): this is even more remarkable inasfar as Chaudhary demonstrates that it was not the Muslims who caused the destruction of the famous monastery (below).

Destruction of Buddhist monuments or the abandonment of sacred areas in relation to the establishment of Brahmanic dynasties are also documented in Deccan. I recall the case of Vijayapuri/Nagarjunakonda, where an interesting dialectics in patronage can be observed. The famous sacred Buddhist areas were built during the times of the Ikṣvākus, and therefore between the second quarter of the 3rd century and the middle of the 4th. The patronage of the strong Buddhist communities was entrusted to the female representatives (as for example Cāṃtaśrī, sister of the first Cāṃtamūla, to whom we owe the construction of the stūpa of site 1) of the ruling household, officially Sivaite, at a time in which Sivaism was as yet incapable of contrasting Buddhist power, and still had not assumed the role of being the bulwark of orthodoxy which later it was the first to play in the South²⁵. None of Cāṃtamūla’s successors is actually reported to have performed any Brahmanical sacrifices, and according to some, it is not improbable that they were Buddhists (see Majumdar & Altekar 1967: 66–7). It was the Pallavas, Brahmans of the Bhāradvāja *gotra* and performers of *aśvamedha*, *vajapeya* and other Vedic rituals (Jayswal 1933: 92; 178 ff.), who

²⁵ It is not easy to evaluate Sivaism as a political–ideological referent through time. In some realities, as in Kuṣāṇa Mathura (the famous temple of Mat was probably Sivaite: see Lüders 1961: 131 ff. and esp. 143–5), in ancient Kathmandu and in northern India at the time of Harṣavardhana, it seems to have been far from an alliance with Brahmanic orthodox lineages, who were growing increasingly pro–Vishnuites, preferring an alliance with the Buddhists (for Kathmandu, see Verardi 1992: 31 ff.). It may be interesting to note, in this regard, that in Kathmandu Śaṅkara “avait alors chassé les bhiksus de Paṅupati et avait institué à leur place des brahmanes du Dekkhan” (Lévi 1905–8, I: 365), those who still officiate there. It actually seems that there is a strong discontinuity in Nepalese Sivaism, and the fact that the change in its strategy is attributed to Śaṅkara can only reinforce the idea of an earlier Sivaite–Buddhist understanding. We know that Śaṅkara, a “reformer”, was not greatly appreciated in the most traditional Brahmanic circles. However, his attempt, crowned by success, to bring the most unruly Sivaite circles to full neo–Vedic orthodoxy, is also detectable in other undertakings attributed to him. I read in Piantelli (1974: 81), who follows the *Prācīnaśaṅkaravijaya*, that at Ujjayīni he convinced a number of Brahmans to abstain from the cult of Śiva in his dog–like aspect of Khandoba: “Ceremonial practices, carried out by a specialized clergy, the Vāghyas, included the ritual barking and proceeding like quadrupeds, taking food from the alm bowls placed on the ground”. In other cases, as in the South (but also in the Northeast at the time of Śaśāṅka) Sivaism occupied a place at the head of the Brahmanic reaction from early on. The ultimate reason could be Sivaite hostility to Vishnuit Brahman in this case too, and the attempt to block their way. What we know of the violent contrast (the episode of Rāmānuja is well–known) opposing Sivaītes and Vishnuites when the latter reached such a level of organization, also in the South, so as to put an end to the traditional Sivaite supremacy, conforms to this explanation.

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seem to have swept the lower Krishna valley, causing the almost total destruction and abandoning of the area (Sarkar & Mishra 1972: 17).

A case that is little known is that of Vengipura, in Andhradesa, where the sacred Buddhist area was built thanks to the patronage of the local dynasty of the Sālaṅkāyaṇas (and specifically, by king Nandivarman II, A.D. 400–30) and was substituted with buildings of the Brahmanic cult (a *pañcayatana* temple in the place of the main stūpa, reutilizing its building materials) by the end of the 5th century, when the orthodox Viṣṇukundins had already supplanted the former rulers²⁶. The Buddhist buildings in Deccan that were replaced by Sivaite temples are numerous²⁷. Sivaism, which was the interpreter of the Brahmanic *revanche*, will later be metabolized by Vishnuism, destined – thanks to its upper hand in the Deccan – to become the winning ideology of Brahmanism in the whole of India. It would be opportune to check, case by case, if this replacement of monuments is contextual (which I think is probable) to persecutions and violence.

We recalled above the transfer of the embryo of Mahāvīra to a Kshatriya womb, which betrays a programmatic distancing of a part of the Kshatriyas from the Brahmins, and an unprecedented split between *sacerdotium* and *regnum*, or rather between what had remained of that remote functional division²⁸. The Buddha was also born into a clan affiliated with the *varṇa* of the Kshatriyas, and in some texts of the Pāli Canon, the overturning of the hierarchical Brahmins/Kshatriyas relationship is explicit, for example, in the *Ambaṭṭha Sutta* of the *Dīgha Nikāya* (I avail myself of the translation by Frola, 1967: 101–24). As we know, the Buddha, as a prince, was the representative of the Kshatriyas, but refused to represent them directly. However, he did much more; he supplied them with a powerful ideological instrument without which even the idea of organizing themselves as opponents of the Brahmins would have been

²⁶ For an evaluation of the archaeological finds at Vengipura see Verardi (1997). Among the early Viṣṇukundin rulers, Govindavarman I stands out, who came to the throne in about A.D. 422. Originally pro-Buddhist, he was one of the first southern kings whom we know converted to Sivaism (as Mahendrarvarman I of the Pallava will also do, for example). It seems evident that these rulers were not able to keep afloat with the only support of the *śramaṇas*, and that realistically, they sought the support of the Brahmins (becoming the persecutors of their previous allies). For the Viṣṇukundins, the reader is referred to Sankaranarayan (1977).

²⁷ The temple of Kamākṣī at Kanechipuram rises above the ruins of a Tāra temple (T.A.G. Rao 1915); the great temple of Srisailam seems to rise above what had once been a Buddhist site (Longhurst 1938: 6). Jaini (1980), discussing the Sivaite temple of Kadri-Maṅjunātha at Mangalore according to lines that I do not agree with, recalls that various Buddhist temples fell into the hands of Hindu groups, even if “the exact sequence of developments whereby such Hindu appropriation took place” remains obscure (p. 87). It would be necessary to make a lengthy study of the available archaeological sources and local traditions, written or oral, to expose the whole picture.

²⁸ For the hierarchic relations of principle between the Brahmins and the Kshatriyas, the reader is referred to Guénon (1930) and Coomaraswamy (1942). Both works lack, as may be expected, any sort of attempt to consider the question in historic terms as well, but it must be said that the first, and for the very reason that it lucidly assumes a Brahmanic-orthodox point of view, is far more penetrating than the second, and sees the question of the “Kshatriya rebels” very clearly.

inconceivable. This is the "revolt of the Kshatriyas", well-known to the sources, even if misunderstood in its real terms or minimized (see e.g. Bhattacharya 1983-4).

Once again it is a myth that helps us in understanding past events. In the *Mahābhārata*, the mirror of Vishnuite neo-orthodoxy, Rāma is depicted as repeatedly slaying the Kshatriyas. He does so a good twenty-one times (*Mahābhārata*, I, 64; III, 117; VII, 70; XII, 14; XIV, 29), each time devoiding the earth of them. The struggle against the Kshatriyas was evidently long and repeated in time, just as the destructions and persecutions that can be historically documented or suspected were repeated, often followed by (as after the Śuṅgas, the Sātavāhanas²⁹, or the Guptas) a new period of "Kshatriya" hegemony, with differing rhythms and modalities, depending on the regions. Indeed, it is against the Kshatriyas holding the power in various regions of India that Rāma, "creating a deluge of blood and filling many lakes also with blood as red as *Indrojopakas*

²⁹ In Indian historiography and in antiquarian studies, it is traditional to attribute all the monuments of Upper Deccan built between the 1st century B.C. and the 2nd century A.D. to the patronage of the Sātavāhanas. But it is very difficult that this was the case. The Sātavāhanas, at the peak of their fortunes, wanted to immortalize their dynasty at Nanaghat (not completely succeeding in this as the images depicting them are lost now) declaring themselves, as we know from the famous, long *prasasti*, to be fully orthodox and faithful to the performance of sacrifices (see it in Sircar 1965: 193-7). They were in a never-ending struggle with the Kṣatrapas, who are better claimants to the role of supporters of the Buddhist institutions (in many cases, we know this for sure). We know, however, of Gautamīputra's decision, once he had defeated Nahapāna in about A.D. 124, to guarantee the Buddhist community of Nasik the rights it had acquired, probably because the community was too important to estrange it with immediate measures against it. The grant we have evidence of regarded a village already assigned by Nahapāna's son Rṣabhadatta, and the order was issued, as we read in the inscription (Sircar 1965: 197-9), from a military camp. This "points to the transference of authority in northern Maharashtra" (Sircar in Majumdar 1968: 201). Hazra (1995: 385) emphasizes that Gautamīputra "always described himself as 'unique Brahmana' 'eka bahmana'", and that he "stopped the mixing of castes".

The most famous archaeological site in Deccan attributed to the patronage of the Sātavāhanas is naturally Amaravati, but there is an increasing awareness that "The early history of Andhra Pradesh is poorly understood, for there is a decided lack of specific information that sheds light on the patronage and chronology of the monuments in the region prior to the second century A.D." (Huntington 1985: 85). Prominent among the donors were the merchants (see Lüders 1912: nos. 1206 ff.), and we should evaluate with great caution the presence of the names of Sātavāhana rulers like Vāsiṣṭhiputra Puṣumavi, Sivamaka Sada (still usually, but wrongly identified with Śivaskanda Śātakarṇi as in Knox 1992: 13) and Gautamīputra Yajña Śātakarṇi. As to the first, his name appears in an inscription which documents the donation of a *dharmaçakra* by a householder and his relatives, and has little to do with the royal patronage of the monument or the protection of the Community. As to the second, recent excavations at the Jain site of Vaddamanu, about 10 kilometers from Amaravati, show that the period between 100 B.C. and A.D. 200 is characterized by the presence of lead coins of the Sada rulers, probably descendants of Khāravela. Three of them are known from Vaddamanu (Maha Sada, Sivamaka Sada, and Asaka Sada). Regarding the second, Sircar (1962: 85) maintains that it is not necessarily true that he is to be identified with a Sātavāhana ruler, having been probably belonged to the Aira family – that which seems to have actually wielded the power in the lower Krishna basin when the Kṣatrapas ruled in Western Deccan, and apparently even later, when the latter were defeated. Coins of the Sātavāhanas appear at Vaddamanu only in around A.D. 200 (Sastri, Kasturibai & Verrender 1992: 24-5). Thapar (1987: 28) is aware that the dynasties of the Śuṅgas and the Sātavāhanas were only marginally involved, if at all, with the monuments traditionally attributed to them.

or the wild fruit called *Vandujiva*" (ib.: VII, 70), proceeds one after the other "against the Kashmiras, the Daradas, the Kuntis, the Kshudrakas, the Malavas, the Angas, the Vangas, the Kalingas, the Videhas, the Tamraliptas, the Rakshovahas, the Vitahotras, the Trigartas, the Martikavatas" (ib.: VI, 134) – in short against all the Kshatriya lineages reigning throughout North India, from Kashmir to Bengal. It is interesting to note that in one passage (I, 104) it is maintained that the Kshatriya "race" was restored by the Kshatriya ladies, cohabiting with the Brahmans: a detail that seems referable to situations of political equilibrium or impasse, like that noted at Nagarjunakonda at the time of the Ikṣvākus, to which the extremist (and victorious) wing of the Brahmans did not intend to adapt itself all the same. Equally significant, in relation to what has been said in these pages, is the passage (VII, 23) in which a Pāṇḍya king, Sāraṅgadhvaja, acquires the weapons of Rāma: we already know for what uses. The difficult and lengthy undertaking of exterminating the Kshatriyas had, at the same time, the objective of re-establishing order on earth and of *restoring the lands that had been taken away from the Brahmans* (VII, 70; XII, 235; XIII, 62 and 137) – the lands that non-Brahmanic institutions, like the monasteries, had gradually taken over, placing themselves in direct competition with the Brahmanic model of society (below). The Puranic literature does little else but repeat what has just been said.

The insistence on the struggle against the Kshatriyas in the late-ancient and medieval sources show that it did not take place in an indistinct period projected into a little known past, as it has been authoritatively claimed (Kosambi 1965: 146) – or however, not only at that time, but in centuries and places whose principal events it would be possible to reconstruct exactly enough if one really wants to. As arduous as it is to evaluate the antiquity of a myth such as that of Rāma (and particularly so its orthodox version), it is unlikely that a similar symbolic figure arose before the beginning of the conflict, as important scholars now supporting fundamentalist positions have been substantially obliged to admit³⁰. Besides, Rāma is the

³⁰ Puranic literature places Rāma in a period earlier than that during which Kṛṣṇa is supposed to have been living. Rāma was born in the *tretā yuga*, and Kṛṣṇa in the *dvāpara yuga*. Many attempts have been made to historicize these two personages who are so central to post-Vedic Brahmanism, among which, those carried out by scholars who consider archaeology as the most objective way of doing so, stand out. B.B. Lal, a famous archaeologist to whom we owe the sequence at Hastinapura (the excavation was aimed at demonstrating the historicity of the *Mahābhārata*: see Lal 1954), has been at the head of the "Rāmāyaṇa Project" as well. Excavations have been carried out by him at several sites (see those at Srīngaverapuram, partly published: Lal 1993) including Ayodhya, where seventeen trenches were made. Contrary to the expectations of many scholars, convinced, on the basis of Puranic calculations, that the *Rāmāyaṇa* episode went back to the 3rd millennium B.C., "the earliest times when all these sites (i.e. those selected for excavations for the "Rāmāyaṇa Project") could have co-existed was that of the early Northern Black Polished Ware" (Lal in Sinha 1989: 7). Lal has honestly admitted that "That the Rāmāyaṇa episode could be as late as the seventh century B.C. shocked many, including, let it be frankly confessed, myself. But howsoever disappointed I may have felt, the key-site of Ayodhyā has refused to yield anything earlier than *circa* 700 B.C., and, as a disciplined archaeologist, I have no option but to submit to the judgement of the Mother earth" (ib.: 9). Lal's intellectual honesty is not common. R.C. Gaur, an archaeologist well-known for the

characteristic hero and *avatāra* of the region in which the clash between the Brahmans and Kshatriyas was paradigmatic, tougher and more protracted in time: eastern Uttar Pradesh and Bihar, i.e. the places of the Buddha and Mahāvīra, those with the greater concentration, in the course of time, of Buddhist institutions. The five lakes of blood which Rāma filled with the blood of the Kshatriyas whom he slew (*Mahābhārata*, I, 2; III, 117) were at Samantapacaka, that is Kurukshetra. It is significant that the Guptas, orthodox supporters of the idea of nation contrasting with Buddhist universalism, elected Ayodhya to their favourite residence. This, to cite Jayaswal (1933: 119), was because it "had the orthodox imperial tradition of Rāma's name (...), a name which embodied the whole of the past Hindu civilization". It would be useful to reconstruct the patronage and the territorial distribution of the images and temples of Rāma and Paraśurāma in an analytical manner, in connection with the establishment, in Northern India, of the Vishnuite hegemony, even considering that, being heroes-*avatāras* who had arisen from the most orthodox milieu, they could certainly not be the subject of iconic *bhakti* very early on³¹. One of the most ancient temples dedicated to Paraśurāmeśvara is the one at Bhuvaneshvara, a place that had been controlled by the Jains and Buddhists for a long time³².

excavations of Atranjikhera (Gaur 1983), unable to deny the evidence, argues that the Ayodhya of the *Rāmāyana* has, so to speak, travelled with the Indo-Arians, being finally identified, in Madhyadesa (the last of their "original territories", as we have seen), with a locality which cannot be the actual place where, much earlier, the events narrated in the *Rāmāyana* took place. These can, therefore, continue to be considered very ancient (Gaur in Sinha 1989: 27 ff.). The date of the 7th century is a little forced (the *NBPW* generally appears a little later), and it is unlikely that the presumed historical Rāma lived exactly during the period to which the first archaeological evidence belongs. It seems clear to me (had I to make the hypothesis of Rāma's historicity my own) that we should bring down his chronology even further, *grosso modo* to the times of the Buddha (leaving aside here the question of which chronology to adopt for the latter) – i.e. to the period in which the conflict we are speaking about in these pages erupted.

³¹ The acceptance by the majority of the Brahmans of the images as cult objects required a lot of time and was greatly opposed. The Bhāgavatas (those who first understood the importance of the new medium) were considered by the Brahmans more rigidly respectful of Vedic orthodoxy as being of lower caste, and up till a relatively late period heavy accusations rained down on them (Dasgupta, 1932–55, III: 14–20). We must wait for the mature Gupta period and the Vidisa manifesto (note 23) to observe a mature, but still limited iconic production. It can be argued that the more orthodox Brahmanic milieu became convinced of the opportunity of supporting the new trend only when, with the Gupta crisis and the re-emergence of politically organized anti-Brahmanic instances, they understood that temple worship could be a more powerful weapon to use against the Buddhists (who had understood the use of image worship for a long time already) than Vedic rituals.

³² It is barely the case to recall the pitiless Kalinga war of Aśoka and the presence of his edicts and of an unfinished rock-cut elephant at Dhauri. The unusual *linga* in the temple of Bhaskarēśvara seems to be a large fragment of an Aśokan pillar (see Panigrahi 1961: 177–210). The identification of the Maurya city, Tosali, with Sisupalgarh, is uncertain. This seems to correspond more closely to the Kalīnganagara spoken about in the Hathigumpha inscription (see, for this question, Lal 1949: 66–7). As for the famous caves of Udayagiri and Khandagiri, no doubt remains (despite the difficulties of iconographic interpretation, which remain) that they are Jain (see e.g. D. Mitra 1960; Huntington 1985: 105 ff.). The abandonment of these sites coincides with the emergence of the Brahmanic temple town of Bhuvaneshvara, of which the temple of Paraśurāmeśvara is one of the oldest and most famous.

I share the opinion of some authors, amongst whom Staal (1985: 17 ff.; 1990 b: 406 ff.), that the search for "original" Buddhism, in the ways in which it has been historically carried out, is futile, but I believe that the fact that Buddhism was born and developed in contiguity and alternative to Brahmanism should be stressed: its cradle was the same territory that had been identified, in the end, with Brāhmavarta. The discussion on Mahāyāna, which still today is often considered as a later phenomenon, should take into account the fact that its development was a reply to Brahmanic pressure, and therefore took place, in India, in different times and ways. It is for this reason that it did not originate from any of the eighteen Buddhist schools; rather it probably was, from the beginning, the most appropriate strategy used in confronting adversary forces, becoming, from a systemic point of view, the most suitable reply to a powerful opponent. The Gnostic strategy of Buddhism was in a position of strong disadvantage when unsupported by political power. Its organization centred around the *Electi* who lived in monasteries, but for some regions like Madhyadesa and the Northwest did not extend everywhere (even if monasteries grew larger and larger), and did not resolve the question of the relationship with laymen. The presence of the Brahmins in the society, instead, could be, and in fact was, increasingly pervasive: there was not a village in which a Brahmin family could not establish itself, directly linked to the clergy. The Mahāyāna resolutely opened to the laymen. It accepted their daily needs and habits, and therefore admitted, from an early time, a certain number of rituals which were the heritage of tradition and of the laymen (see e.g. Verardi 1994): in this – in noting that it is not the rituals that change, but their doctrinal interpretations – Staal is certainly right, but only partly, because it should be observed that until it could, *Buddhism drastically selected the rituals that it considered necessary to include in its own system*. All bloody rituals and those pertinent to the political sphere, actually a great many, were excluded. The Mahāyāna also developed what could be called a salvational subsystem centred on the Bodhisattvas, those enlightened beings who are determined to save the greatest number of living beings possible³³. This opening to laymen was counterbalanced by an accentuating, or in any case by an unambiguous expression of the original Gnostic characteristics: the *bodhicitta*, or "thought of the enlightenment", is the same as the spark that the Pneumatics recognized in themselves, the development of which made it possible to leave the world (*this* world, as we have seen, governed by old gods, their priests and old ruling classes)³⁴.

³³ This is a rather early development in Buddhism, because in Kuṣāṇa times Śākyamuni is docetically conceived as a Heavenly Being descended from on high to save mankind: for this reason, in most inscribed images of the period (see the list in Härtel 1985: 656–7), he is labelled *bodhisattva* (and not *buddha*) i.e. one who, after reaching *nirvāṇa*, would not descend again into *saṃsāra*. I dealt with the question in an article (Verardi 1985) which would require some revision. I do not share the opinion of Jaini (1980) who, in a comparison of the survival strategies of the Buddhists and the Jains, finds the weak point in the bodhisattva theory.

³⁴ The Mahāyāna does not betray "original" Buddhism, but provides it with better arms with which to oppose the rival model. There is little sense in comparing it, outside any historical analysis,

The progressive spreading of Mahāyāna coincided historically with the partial transformation of the social base of Buddhism. The monasteries had played the crucial card of trade revolution, a development model that was powerful and at the same time risky with respect to the well-established one based on the exploitation of agricultural resources. The abandonment of a trade route or its decline, especially if linked to the variables of long-distance trade, could mean the collapse of important establishments (think of the lot of many monasteries in Western Deccan). From the 3rd century onwards, the crisis of the trade economy became increasingly profound. The decline of the Indian cities began, which caused the de-urbanization of the country already in Gupta times (Sharma 1987; a number of excavation reports should be seen in greater detail). This was the moment in which the Brahmanic social and economic model, based on land, regained the upper hand. I would like to underline, in this regard, that I do not believe that the new social order that India was preparing depended on the general, changed state of the economic fundamentals (the rise of Islam demonstrates that the conditions of economic stalemate could be successfully overcome by relying on trade, to the point of transforming a very large number of regions very different from each other into a great urban and mercantile civilization). On the contrary, I think that Brahmanic ideology, which had always been hostile to anything that questioned the social equilibrium attained in the rural areas, exerted a fundamental function in determining the decline of the urban and mercantile economy of the subcontinent, the struggle against which coincided basically with the struggle against the Buddhists and Jains. The "Brahmanic model" did not prevail because of objective and uncontrollable factors; on the contrary, it was actively pursued and constructed.

In the new situation, the monasteries, who for some time already had benefited from land grants (the earliest are documented in Junnar; see Burgess & Bhagwanlal 1881: nos. 9, p. 44; 13, p. 45; 17 and 18, p. 48; for an example at Nasik see note 29), conformed to the situation. The great monasteries of Bihar and Bengal of the 8th-9th centuries represent the final outcome of this transformation³⁵. With the Pālas, who generally defined themselves as *paramasaugatas* (see e.g. Sircar 1975), they succeeded in attracting, in Northern India, the last organized political forces opposing the orthodox dynasties (in Deccan, as we know from Tāranātha, as well as from much archaeological evidence, the game had already been lost; see Chattopadhyaya 1970: 225). It was over the ownership of land, as shown very clearly by the myth of Rāma, and,

to Theravāda Buddhism, the strategies of which enjoyed great success in regions of Asia where there was no cultural élite as powerful and prestigious as the Brahmanic one. I wonder if the Mahāyānists considered their vehicle "great" also for other reasons than those connected to the spiritual salvation of individuals and, with a certain contempt, "small", the vehicle of the Theravādins and other schools that were less successful in opposing the Brahmanic domination.

³⁵ We know of numerous donations of villages made to the monastery of Nalanda starting from that, of a good hundred villages, of Harṣavardhana (see Beal 1911: 112). For other donations of villages recorded in inscriptions, see e.g. Sastri (1942: 84-5: 92 ff., esp. lines 26-37).

But 'monastic'
 merged vehicles
 Chakrasamudra

even more, against a "free market" economy, that the final battle was fought (as also happened in China; see Verardi, in the press a). When it was over, the land had passed to the new Brahmanic temples, which in fact began to characterize the landscape of northern India and the Vindhya exactly at that turn in time, from Kashmir to Orissa, becoming ever more numerous and ever larger, as the decline of the monasteries became increasingly evident.

A fundamental pawn in the anti-Buddhist struggle was the call to the concept of orthodoxy, around which, thanks to personages like Śaṅkara, the Brahmanic response could organize itself. I have hinted above at the fact that Staal has suggestively maintained that in the Indian world (but also in the Far East), orthodoxy is much less important than orthopraxis. The two concepts actually pertain to different levels, and their importance can only be measured according to the field under investigation. *The concept of orthodoxy can be superimposed on that of truth and legitimacy, and for this reason, can be used politically. The concept of orthopraxis cannot, or else only to a limited degree.* In India there are many orthopraxes within the frame established by the Veda which do not question the general principle of identity and ultimate authority, that is, orthodoxy. It was on the latter that the Brahmans organized themselves *politically*: orthopraxis followed. One of the reasons for which the Brahmans came out on top is that the Jains and the Buddhists did not have the instruments to oppose them with a different orthodoxy: given the fundamentals of their systems they could do little else but denounce the absurdity of a like concept³⁶.

The End

I think it useful to go back to Kathmandu in order to clarify what the events that took place there meant for the following, and last, phase in the history of

³⁶ An example made by Staal more than once (1985: 34–6; 1990a: 26; 1990b: 395–6) is that, based on a pioneering study by Jest (1964–5), of the Thākālis, a community which controls trade along the upper course of the Gandaki in Nepal. Staal emphasizes how, according to the historical-social conditions, they have considered themselves Buddhists or Hindus, their rules and rituals remaining unchanged. To me this seems possible (it must have happened on a number of occasions with several social groups) because the Thākālis are the Thākālis – because, that is, they occupy a low position in the Brahmanic social hierarchy. For the Brahmans of Kathmandu the Thākālis do not constitute any form of inconvenience, and even less a threat, even when the pendulum leads them towards Buddhism. There is no conflict if the Brahmanic balance of a certain period is not questioned. Doctrinal indifference is not (and never was) a characteristic of the upper segments of the Brahmanic hierarchy (i.e. the élite which takes decisions), *but rather of the lower and marginal segments, which are subject to oscillation exactly for being so.* Such a statement by Staal that "... in many of the traditional societies of South, Southeast and East Asia, rituals are not necessarily associated with doctrinal superstructures or belief systems: that is, *they are rituals without religion*" (Staal 1986: 207; his emphasis) can only be accepted at the "anthropological" level, that which considers such things as doctrine (or politics, art, etc.) as "superstructures" and not as activities that are to be considered, like rituals, *per se*. See below in the text.

Indian Buddhism, of which they are an important trace. The excavation at Harigaon mentioned earlier has shown that the sacred Buddhist area of Andigrama was substituted by a Vishnuite temple, and that in around A.D. 800, the village changed its name to Harigaon, the "village of [the temple of] Hari", the village whose revenues had been assigned for the maintenance of the Hari temple (Verardi 1992: 21, n. 48). According to the tradition preserved in the Buddhist *vaṃśāvalīs*, following the reaction that was raised also in Nepal by Śaṅkara (or by others like him)³⁷, the Buddhists who did not want to submit and reach a compromise were killed. Those who gave in were forced to sacrifice animals; the nuns and monks were obliged to get married (see Wright 1877: 118 ff.). "Shankaracharya thus destroyed the Buddhist religion, and allowed none to follow it; but he was obliged to leave Baudhamargis in some places as priests of temples, where he found that no other persons would be able to propitiate the gods placed in them by great Baudhamargis" (ib.: 120). In other words, the Buddhist resistance was so determined that not enough Brahmans could be found who were ready to substitute the Buddhist institutions. A tradition that is still alive at Patan, told by Gellner (1987: 390–1), tells of a king who expropriated the lands of a *bahī*, sent the celibate monks who lived there to beg, for that was their work, and forced them to marry, in other words, to live in almost impossible conditions, given that "the sixty-four kinds of work had already been given to the sixty-four castes". The annihilation of Buddhism was contextual to the full (re)-establishment of an orthodox caste society.

The pressure on the Buddhists who had not been killed or who had not fled was very strong, to such a degree that it accounts for the particularities that distinguish Newar Buddhism, a presumed "confused mixture of Hinduism and Buddhism... of little interest to a student of Buddhism", as Locke (1980: xiv) complained not many years ago that most scholars thought. One of the most important features of Newar Buddhism is the performance, which is executed in different ways depending on the caste, of life-cycle rites parallel to the Brahmanic ones (see now Gellner 1992: 197 ff.). Another feature is precisely the fact that Newar Buddhists are divided into castes according to hierarchies which reflect "Hindu" caste division. A third feature is that the priest caste, made up of *vajrācāryas*, corresponding in status and functions to the *rājopādhyāya* Brahmans (ib.: 43 ff.; 258 ff. and *passim*) is situated at the top of the system. In short, Newar Buddhism was forced to model itself entirely on the structures and values of Brahmanic society and ideology.

The close link between this situation with that, described above, of medieval

³⁷ Historians usually judge both the Nepalese sojourn of Śaṅkara and his initiatives against the Buddhists as legendary. See for instance Petech (1984: 203), who nonetheless takes the evidence given by Wiesner (1980; see note 24 above) into serious consideration, and naturally did not know the results of the excavations at Harigaon. There are many reasons to doubt the actual presence of Śaṅkara at Kathmandu. However, all over India, there are too many traditions which credit him with the defeat of Buddhism not to believe that there were decisive actions against it during his times.

Jainism is obvious. In Nepal, in order to survive, Buddhism had to submit as well to a sort of mimicry of the Brahmanic society, and in order to distance itself so as to maintain its own identity, it preserved, and further elaborate, particular forms of esoterics (in which the high "Tantric" initiates are the equivalent of the ancient *āryas*, the repositories of gnosis). Naturally, an essential for survival was the acceptance of the status of being politically excluded: the time of the Kshatriyas (the early ones, those issued from the Indo-Aryan élite) was over. But even in these conditions, survival was difficult, and was only made possible by the divarication, starting from late medieval times, of Nepalese history from that of the rest of India. At the beginning of this century, Sylvain Lévi wrote that the Buddhists of Nepal "ne savent rien que les seuls noms des neuf *dharmas* népalais (...). Le bouddhisme se meurt ici: stūpas et *čaityas* se reconcentrent partout encore, mais à l'intérieur de la ville ils sont abandonnés et à demi ruinés. Les seuls fidèles qui leur restent sont les basses classes rejetées dans les faubourgs, et les Tibétains malpropres" (Lévi 1905–8, II: 325). The tourists have arrived just in time.

As was the case for Jainism, growing pressure was exerted on to Newar Buddhism, upon which improper roles, like the marriage of monks, were imposed, and which was forcibly fit in a caste cage where no freedom was left for independent developments. It was obliged to accept the performance of rituals, the presence and nature of which, contrary to Staal's claims, *can only be explained by history and doctrine. Far from being an unimportant third, doctrine appears as the only bulwark for the safeguard of an entire system*, which can reveal itself capable of regaining initiative and reaffirming its identity in historically changed conditions: *it is doctrine, and not rituals, that forms the core of a system.*

To the south of the Siwaliks things went no differently. They are more difficult to understand because Muslim conquest profoundly changed the course of events. Even in India, Buddhism managed to survive. The Buddhist institutions of the 11th and 12th centuries were, in Madhyadesa and in the East, still relatively numerous, even if (rather: because) by then they lacked any real weight. In a period when Buddhism was no longer capable of threatening, on a general level, Brahman hegemony, it could also be the object of patronage: for example, by Govindacandra of the Gāhaḍavālas of Kanauj (see Majumdar in Majumdar 1966: 422–3; Hazra 1995: 157 ff.). But wherever it continued to represent or to be perceived as a threat, it was systematically repressed. We can recall the anti-Buddhist persecution of Jātavarman of the Yādava dynasty of East Bengal towards the end of the 11th century (ib.: 34) or, during the same period, that of king Harṣa of Kashmir, who ordered the melting down of all metal Buddhist images, after having them publicly defiled by leprous beggars who voided urine and excrement upon them (cf. Kosambi 1965: 186).

In Mithila, for centuries known as one of the bulwark-regions of Brahman orthodoxy and, before that, home to a dense network of Buddhist institutions (we are between Bihar and the central part of the Nepalese Tarai), the conflict ended in a great deal of bloodshed (contrary to those who claim that it was, even if marked by some excess, only doctrinal). I recall, together with Upendra Thakur (1956: 434), the reciprocal massacres of the 7th century and the facts recorded in

the Brahmanic sources like the writings of Udayana, the famous philosopher of Mithila who lived in the 10th century, the *Vaṃaratnākara* by Jyotirīśvara (minister of Harisīmhadēva, who was still ruling in Simraongarh during the first half of the 14th century) and other texts as well. It is evident that "the wordy war and mutual hatred and jealousy between the adherents of the two systems had reached such a dangerous point that it often culminated in violent bloodsheds and massacres" (ib.: 435). A King Sudhanvā of Mithila "drowned, by order of Śaṅkara, thousands of Buddhists into the ocean and mercilessly massacred them" (ib. 439–40; the source is Mādhava's *Śaṅkara-digvijaya*).

These sources also show that, contrary to the claims of many authors who use their "silence" as a shield to protect their own views, the material to be analysed regarding the facts spoken about here is certainly not lacking³⁸.

In the eastern regions, where Buddhism survived even longer (the great monastery of Ratnagiri in Orissa survived until the 16th century: see D. Mitra 1981–3: 23–4), there were still persecutions at the times of king Pratāparudra during the first half of the 16th century (Eliot 1921, II: 115). From the works of the poets Acyutānāda Dāsa and Caitanya Dāsa, in which Kṛṣṇa is constantly identified with *śūnya*, we know that in the Kali age the followers of the Buddha had to disguise themselves, and that there were three thousand "crypto-Buddhists" hidden in various parts of Orissa (cf. ib.). From the "mimicry" of Brahmanism they had proceeded to the penultimate passage before disappearing.

Conventional historiography is unanimous in ascribing to the Muslims the responsibility for the end of Buddhism in India. *The History and Culture of the Indian People*, the outcome and basis of a fundamentally nationalistic historiography, could be cited in a number of cases. We will refer to only two brief passages, in which indisputable facts (not all) are presented within an unacceptable paradigm:

"The Brahmanical religion has always showed its catholicity by absorbing powerful rival religious sects. At a much earlier period it brought the cults of both Kṛishṇa-Vāsudeva and Rudra-Śiva within its fold. Now it repeated the same process in regard to Buddhism by declaring the Buddha to be an incarnation of Viṣṇu. The developed doctrines and rituals of Mahāyāna and Brahmanical religion made such a near approach to each other, specially through the stress upon faith and devotion, worship of images of numerous gods and goddesses, and the use of Sanskrit in liturgical texts, on the part of the Buddhists, and the acceptance of the principle of *ahimsā*, specially in regard to diet, that a merger of the two was not only rendered quite easy but became almost inevitable. The identification of Buddha with Viṣṇu by means of the theory of incarnation completed the process, and Buddhism silently merged itself into Brahmanical religion" (Majumdar 1966: 402).

"The brief sketch given above leaves no doubt that Buddhism was a living force in many parts of Northern India down to the end of the twelfth century (...) But the invasion of the Muslims and the ruthless destruction of Buddhist monasteries by them finally extinguished the lamp of Buddhism that was still flickering in the plains of North India. The vivid description, by an almost contemporary Muslim writer, of the wanton destruction of the great monasteries at

³⁸ As to the level of doctrinal polemics, Bharati (1977: 21) observes that modern Brahman scholars who do not know western literature on Indian thought well and who, for this reason, are not influenced by it, continue to oppose the Buddhist doctrines more or less with the same violence of their classic predecessors.

Uddandapura (Bihar) and the wholesale massacre of its shaven-headed monks, gives us an idea of how the great monasteries of Nālandā, Vikramasīla and others of less renown met with a sudden and tragic end" (ib.: 425).

The real end of Buddhism, as we have seen, precedes, and by a large margin, the first Muslim raids, and even more so the actual establishment of Muslim power. What Islam did put an end to (it would be opportune to make a careful case by case examination) was the simulacrum of what Buddhism had been. The facts which at a first sight seem to support the traditional thesis are certainly not lacking. But not everything is clear. Despite the condition of inferiority to which Buddhist institutions had been reduced, on the eve of the Muslim invasion of Bihar, Brahmanic pressure continued to be very strong (Askari & Ahmad 1983: 32), and even after the attacks by the Turks of Bakhtiyār Khaljī against some monasteries, the *tīrthikas* were responsible for grave destructions yet again, as the burning of the Nalanda library, the Ratnodadhī, years after the establishment of Turkish rule (ib.: 39–40; I read about the episode in H. Sastri 1942: 7–8). Authors who give different evaluations of the chronology of events (Patil 1963: esp. 304, 325; Askari & Ahmad 1983: 39–40) are agreed in not believing in Bakhtiyār's responsibility. (A careful investigation would be necessary not only to shed light on the actual dynamics of events that marked the end of this great Buddhist establishment, but also on episodes of its earlier life. The relationship between the Buddhist buildings and the stone Sivaite temple known in archaeological reports as Site no. 2 is not at all clear: see its description in Deva & Agrawala 1950).

A careful analysis of Antichak–Vikramasīla has been carried out, as we have seen above, by Chaudhary (1978), who also has shown that Bakhtiyār did not even pass through Vikramasīla; the monastery had been in crisis for a long time because of the continuous Brahmanic attacks. The "political convulsions inside the campus or around it" had led to its transformation into a fortress by a Canaka king (mentioned by Tāranātha)³⁹ not belonging to the line of the Pālas. In the final reckoning, "The local population consisting mostly of the Hindus must have sided with the invading armies (of the Hindu or Muslim) from east and west" (p. 232). The ruinous Muslim attack on Uddandapura, which seems to have come about because the walled *vihāra* had been mistaken for a military fort (Askari & Ahmad 1983: 37) can perhaps be related to a similar dynamics of the events.

Leaving aside – as they are much older – the events of the time of Puṣyamitra, when the Buddhists sought an alliance with the Indo-Greeks, we know that in Bihar there were monks who, in order to defend themselves from the Brahmanic reaction of the Senas, sided with the Turks (ib.: 38). The suspicion arises that the destructions caused by the latter were induced, at least in certain cases, by the Brahmins themselves. In other parts of India, the Buddhists,

³⁹ Chaudhary, however, shows that Tāranātha confuses the dates in relation with the end of Vikramasīla (the Turuṣkas could not have been active in Bihar in the last quarter of the 10th century; see p. 230).

evidently in search of allies, had already sought the support of the Muslims: in Sind, for example, where as early as the period of the Arab invasion the Buddhists of Siwistan had reacted to the recent imposition of the Brahmanic lineage of Chach, who, around the middle of the 7th century, had overwhelmed the Buddhist Rais (Lambrick 1973: esp. 171; 185–6). When in the end the Muslims established their rule in India, they seem to have considered the Buddhists as having disappeared from India for a very long time. In Kashmir, when they assumed power in the 14th century, there were no longer any Buddhists. Abū'l-Faḥl 'Allāmī was to write that “for a long time past scarce any trace of them has existed in Hindustan” ('Allāmī 1927–49, III: 224). The scores with the Buddhists had been settled by others. It is not a question of acquitting the Muslims, who, judging from the tiny religious minorities living in the territories they have conquered (excepting only India, where they found in the Brahmans a particularly tough opposer) cannot be considered as an example of tolerance even with regard to the other “peoples of the Book”, but to give to each his own⁴⁰.

Conclusions. In Search of an Explanation.

The facts considered in these pages appear, even against one's own will, to be a sort of a general interpretation of the ancient and medieval history of India,

⁴⁰ It can be interesting, at the end of the discussion, to consider the relationship of the Brahmans with the three different groups that entered India from Iran in different periods: the Magas, the Bhojakas, and the Parsees. The first, apparently corresponding to a priestly class, reached India no later than the 1st century B.C., probably following the Śaka invasion (Stietencron 1966: 234). Thanks to their firm acceptance of the Veda (ib.: 250–1), they were given a high status and could organize the cult of the Sun god, which was not foreign to India, but lacked a particular characterization at the level of the *bhakti* and of the rituals. We know that during the first centuries of our era, there were six classes of *sauras*, or sun worshippers, who had a mantra of eight syllables in common (Banerjee 1948: 50). The plaque with Sūrya on his chariot in a woman's headdress from Kankali Tila (Mathura) is a sign of the religious affiliation of the devotee (cf. Pandey 1971: 77) who, according to the assumptions of *bhakti*, recognized Surya as the creator, protector and destroyer of the universe at the same time. As we know, the images of the god became a part of the Indian pantheon, and autonomous temples to him were built in India and the Indianized regions. The orthodoxy of the cult was guaranteed by the fact that Samba, son of Kṛṣṇa, was taken as the founder of the *mūlasthāna*, the “original seat” of the cult of Sūrya at Multan: so claims the *Sambapurāṇa* (see Stietencron 1966: 17 ff.; 183 ff.). What happened to the Magas can actually be considered as the voluntary “extinguishing” of a particular “high” historical identity into the equally high Brahmanic tradition. In Medieval times, the eclipse of the Sun cult seems due to the fact that the Bhojakas, who entered India in the 6th–7th century A.D. (ib.: 243) became their supporters and representatives. As they held fast to the *Avesta* (contrary to the Magas), they were considered the like of the *śūdras* (ib.: 246) and were progressively isolated, and the cult of Sūrya was abandoned. It was Viṣṇu (presenting solar characters since the beginning) who incorporated the characteristics of the Sun god. As for the Parsees, there are reasons to consider their history as closely resembling that of the Jains, which explains their early and radical support of the process of modernization and westernization of India. After the Parsees entered and established themselves in the subcontinent (in Gujarat), they turned largely away from the principles of their religion, but kept the *Avesta* as the ultimate foundation of their identity. Their priests in particular, the dasturs and mobeds, were organized in hereditary castes in the same way as the Brahmans (Kamerkar 1988: 172), coming to form a sort of clergy parallel to that of the Brahmans (as happened to the Jains and Newar Buddhists). When, in 1721, Jamasp could visit them from Iran,

based on the recognition of the existence of two basic tendencies in ancient Indian society, respectively represented by the Brahmanic ideology and the non-orthodox movements. Such tendencies can be recognized, as time goes on, only on a politico-religious level, with the risk of being unappreciated. The evaluation of factors such as the sense of identity and belonging, ideology, the actions of particular élites, the organization of political consensus and power, and totalitarian logic, becomes most important, because they increasingly appear to be of such weight as to determine, or strongly condition, other crucial factors, such as the economic one, and to overshadow them.

Such an interpretation cannot be easily accepted by the three principal trends of Indian historiography: the national, anti-colonialist one, the Marxist, and that stemming from anthropological and sociological researches. For the first, these two conflictual tendencies, if ever they existed, could not be referred to as the ideological representatives of conflicting forces. This trend (which on a political level has fed the Congress Party) has aimed, on the level of values, at identifying the lay tolerance of a modern democracy with the (imaginary) religious tolerance of the past. Like other countries, modern India could have used modern lay values politically in opposition to past obscurantism if its struggle for independence and its process of modernization had not the Brahmins as a leading force. Even the most critical of them cannot but support the (supposed) positive specificity of the past history of India – which acquits and legitimizes them.

For the historiography of Marxist tradition, the proposed interpretation cannot but make one smile. Religious and ethnic identities, ideological factors and even the role of the élites (obviously crucial in Marxist theory and praxis) are however related to their necessary economic “base”. This even happens in the most sophisticated Marxist analyses, which can consider these factors as very important, but never as decisive. D.D. Kosambi, for whom “The question of the ‘restauration of Hinduism’ or of some king being Buddhist or Hindu is meaningless” (1965: 181), has nevertheless maintained that the two models that here we have called Brahmanic and Kshatriya could exist side by side in ancient times because they represented social and economic milieus that were so remote one from the other that they could ignore each other, and that the conflict exploded in Medieval times because the hunting grounds had become common property (ib.: 182). *But the fact is that the conflict erupted with great violence early on*⁴¹: the

he found that the community was totally ignorant of the ancient traditions (ib.: 174; the words of Sylvain Lévi, quoted above, regarding the Buddhists of Kathmandu at the beginning of the century, come to mind). The recovery of an identity that was almost lost was possible thanks to the changed framework of Indian history: the reformatory movement ultimately led to forms of modernism, rather than to the restoration of the ancient traditions.

⁴¹ Not recognizing this leads even Thapar (1987: 19) to believe that hostility towards Buddhism and Jainism began about the middle of the first millennium A.D. Actually, Thapar does not credit the Brahmanic reaction against the pro-*śramana* policy of the Mauryans led by Puṣyamitra (Thapar 1997: 200; her opinions on this point are not updated in the *Afterword*), nor does she give heed to the orthodox Gupta reaction embodied by Rāma's deeds against the Kshatriyas.

Mauryan model of state, especially with Aśoka, is, as far as we can understand it, diametrically opposed to the Vedic–Brahmanic one, imposed from on high by multiplying the presence of heterodox institutions in the society, specifically chosen and supported to corner the Brahmans.

As to modern historiography nourished by anthropological concepts (to which Staal's positions is, at least partly, to be referred), we could say that the factors which, in my opinion, are decisive in the historical explanation, do not even exist for it in a certain sense. Here the level of the research is constantly kept "below" similar themes: the analysis of events prescind from "high" categories, and the more meaningful they are thought to be the less they are thought to be susceptible of investigation according to such categories as the political ones. The modern archaeological approach is typical of this line of thought, often deaf to everything that is not more or less explicitly related to the knowledges to be found in the "material culture", which, accumulating and being stratified, get the better, in the long run, over and above any other factor. But the point is that the periods of time considered in historical analysis, even if long, as in our case (from the 5th–4th centuries B.C. to Medieval times), are not long enough to allow us to make a meaningful use of such methodology.

I happen to share post-Marxist and historical–anthropological positions. But the decisive factors in historical explanations seem to me, in many cases, to be others. I am often inclined to move along the historiographic and sociological lines inaugurated by Max Weber, who has never been popular in India because he has been simply considered as a scholar who has misunderstood and underestimated – and this is true – important achievements and trends of ancient Indian history⁴². I find myself even closer to evaluating facts according to the categories of classical and Renaissance historiography exactly because of the methodological inadequacy and conceptual limits of which it has been accused in modern times. In identifying crucial motivations at the basis of historical events, a historian like Guicciardini (to make an example) seems to me to be less ideological, more acute and impartial than many modern historians.

I want to conclude by saying that in the conflict between the Brahmans on one hand and the Buddhists and Jains on the other, we can glimpse mechanisms of annihilation that appear as unrestrainable as the reasons that caused them appear vague. Kosambi (who, as a Marxist, could not admit how crucial the conflict between the Brahmans and Buddhists had been, and even less that extermination played any significant role in the substitution of one economic

⁴² A dispassionate analysis of Weber's positions on India has been made by Thapar (1992: 22–59, esp. 41ff.), who has rightly observed that he is to be criticized for not applying his own methodology to his sources on India, contrary to what he did for the source material he had for western history (p. 54). As regards Buddhism (whose role in ancient Indian history has been particularly underestimated by Weber), it is characteristically associated by him to such movements as Gnosticism, which has been misunderstood as well right up to the present (see Verardi, in the press b).

model with another), maintained that "It is difficult today to grasp just what the controversy was about, for the difference between the protagonists seems to be negligible in content, if not in form as well" (Kosambi 1965: 180). Most differences between several protagonists of the history of our century, who nonetheless have been responsible for incredibly ruthless exterminations, will, no doubt, appear to be negligible in future. Even the large amount of information available will not suffice to make such differences clearer, unless one is prepared to take motivations of a different order into account, which may seem moralistic at first, but instead are historical. I have been convinced for a long time, and continue to be so, that many aspects of the Brahmanization of India can be explained by Gramsci's concept of "hegemony" (first theorized by the Jesuits). It is, however, insufficient. Hegemony implies the full control of a society, leaving a number of social and political subjects (relatively) autonomous, but never implies planned and continuous violence. The categories used by some historians of our century in attempting to explain the totalitarian logic can help in the analysis of some aspects of India's past, even if the "Brahman model" cannot historically be defined as totalitarian.

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Abbreviations:

- AI *Ancient India*. New Delhi.
 AO *Ars Orientalis*. Ann Arbor.
 ASI Archaeological Survey of India.
 EW *East and West*. Rome.
 HCPI The History and Culture of the Indian People, ed. R.C. Majumdar, 11 vols. Bombay 1951-69.
 JBRS *Journal of the Bihar Research Society*. Patna.
 MASI Memoirs of the Archaeological Survey of India.

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Fig. 1 – Tiruvattur, Reliefs showing impalement of Jains. (Photo courtesy French Institute of Pondicherry / École Française d'Extrême-Orient).

Fig. 2 – Tiruvattur. Detail of preceding. (Photo courtesy French Institute of Pondicherry / École Française d'Extrême-Orient).

Fig. 3 – Tiruvattur. Detail of fig. 1. (Photo courtesy French Institute of Pondicherry / École Française d'Extrême-Orient).

Fig. 4 – Melakkadambur. Impalement of Jains before Kulaccirai. (Photo courtesy French Institute of Pondicherry / École Française d'Extrême-Orient).

Fig. 5 – Tirupudaimarudur. Impalement of Jains by order of Kulaccirai. (Photo courtesy French Institute of Pondicherry / École Française d'Extrême-Orient).

Fig. 6 – Avudayarkovil. Impalement of Jains after ordeal. (Photo courtesy French Institute of Pondicherry / École Française d'Extrême-Orient).

Fig. 7 – Avudayarkovil. Ordeal in the Vaigai river (left) and impalement of Jains (right). (Photo courtesy French Institute of Pondicherry / École Française d'Extrême-Orient).

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